
Oyster Restoration Quick Assessment Monitoring Guide

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1.0 Introduction and Background

Oysters play an essential role in many estuaries, providing multiple ecosystem services including fisheries harvest, water filtration, shoreline protection, and habitat for other organisms (Beck et al., 2011; Coen et al., 2007; Grabowski & Peterson, 2007; Smith & Pruett, 2025). The eastern oyster, *Crassostrea virginica*, is a reef-building species of oyster that provides essential habitat throughout the Indian River Lagoon (IRL), as well as the larger eastern coast of North America, and Gulf of Mexico. Globally, the majority of oyster reef habitat has been lost or degraded (Beck et al., 2011). In the Indian River Lagoon, a highly impacted coastal region, the devastating loss of oyster reef habitat can be attributed to a variety of factors including altered water flow, habitat loss, sea-level rise, boating impacts, isolated populations, and invasive species (Kyzar et al., 2021; Radabaugh et al., 2019). The dominant driver of oyster degradation varies regionally in the IRL. In the St Lucie Estuary (SLE), the body of water connecting the IRL with the St Lucie River, large freshwater releases from Lake Okeechobee have led to unfavorable conditions for oyster growth and persistence; meanwhile, in the southern IRL basin, the main driver of decline is less obvious (Parker & Radigan, 2020). Over the last few decades, non-profits and municipalities addressed oyster reef loss in the IRL region through developing oyster reef restoration projects, aiming to bring back lost eastern oyster habitat and associated ecosystem services (Beck et al., 2011; Zu Ermgassen et al., 2013). Throughout the 2010s, Florida Oceanographic Society and Martin County established multiple oyster reef restoration project sites, to mitigate the loss of eastern oyster reefs in the southern IRL and SLE.

The short-term results of oyster restoration are well-studied. However, we do not have much information about how long these restored reefs last and what long-term ecosystem services they provide to the estuary (Baggett et al., 2015; Hemraj et al., 2022; Kennedy et al., 2011; La Peyre et al., 2014). Because restored reefs are often not monitored long-term (Table 1.1), monitoring information typically does not capture the development of ecosystem services, despite restored reefs often being constructed of lasting materials (Hemraj et al., 2022; Kennedy et al., 2011; La Peyre et al., 2014; Smith et al., 2023). Restoration sites may not receive appropriate long-term monitoring due to lack of funding and resources, short-term regulatory requirements for monitoring, and unclear restoration goals (L. P. Baggett et al., 2015). Little is known about the timescales to full ecological recovery for restored oyster reefs (Hemraj et al., 2022).

Table 1.1: Monitoring recommendations for human-made oyster reefs.

Source	Human-made oyster reef monitoring recommendation
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The Nature Conservancy (L. Baggett, 2014)	Monitor at 1-2 years and 4-6 years post-implementation
The Nature Conservancy (Brumbaugh et al., 2006)	Annual monitoring for 5 years post-implementation
FDEP Environmental Resource Permitting (Hansen et al., 2024)	Monitoring for 2 years minimum post-implementation

The goal of this Quick Assessment Monitoring Guide is to encourage long-term monitoring of oyster reef restoration projects in the Indian River Lagoon region, providing methodologies, resources, and recommendations for practitioner reference, while shedding light on ecological function of aging restored oyster reefs in the southern IRL and SLE.

2.0 Objectives and Study Design

To better understand the ecological function of aging restored oyster reefs, we designed an observational study to compare mature artificial oyster reef sites to existing natural reefs in the southern IRL and SLE. This study serves as the basis of this Quick Assessment Monitoring Guide and focuses on three categories of ecological services: 1) oyster reef development, persistence, and health, 2) shoreline protection, and 3) habitat provisioning (Table 2.1).

Table 2.1: List of ecological services measured and methodologies used.

Oyster reef development, persistence, and health metrics	Methodology	Page	Appendix
Oyster settlement	Spat Ts	8	A
Substrate composition	Quadrat sampling	12	B
Oyster density	Quadrat sampling	12	B
Size class frequencies	Quadrat sampling	12	B
Oyster species composition	Collection of boxed oysters	12	B
Reef area	Trimble handheld GPS	24	B
Reef height and submergence time	Level and string	24	B
Rugosity	Chain & tape	24	B
Condition Index	Collection of live oysters	30	C
Prevalence & intensity of Dermo disease	Collection of live oysters	36	D

Shoreline protection metrics	Methodology	Page	Appendix
Wave attenuation	DIY Arduino wave gauges	42	E
Sediment accumulation	Sediment plates	46	F
Sediment composition	Sediment core samples	46	F

Habitat provisioning metrics	Methodology	Page	Appendix
Motile macroinvertebrate & small fish abundance	Habitat trays	48	G, I, J
Motile Macroinvertebrate & small fish diversity	Habitat trays	48	G, I, J

Other metrics	Methodology	Page	Appendix
Water quality	HOBO conductivity loggers	55	H

2.1 Site Selection

In the summer months of 2025, 12 intertidal reef sites were sampled including six aging artificial reefs (three artificial reefs in the SLE, three artificial reefs in the southern IRL) and six natural reefs (three natural reefs in the SLE, three natural reefs in the southern IRL; Figure 2.1; Tables 2.2 and 2.3). All of the artificial reef sites included in this study were originally deployed between 2011 and 2018 by Florida Oceanographic Society and Martin County, with sites consisting of multiple modules of aquaculture mesh bags filled with clean oyster shell-cultch (Figure 2.2). These 7 to 14 year-old human-made intertidal oyster reefs will be referred to as artificial reefs for the remainder of this guide, since the modules were not always placed where natural reefs previously existed. Artificial reefs were originally deployed from 2011 to 2018, with practitioners implementing small additions to the projects as recently as 2020 at some sites (Figure 2.2). All aging artificial reefs in the study have exceeded 6 years post-construction, which was identified by Smith et al. (2023) as the timeline within which restored reefs match natural reefs in oyster abundance, oyster biomass, and abundance of mud crabs in Chesapeake Bay. Due to the lack of natural oyster reef sites in the southern IRL near Jensen Beach and Stuart, three natural reefs near the Fort Pierce inlet were used in the study to compare artificial reefs in the southern IRL to natural reefs experiencing similar temperature and salinity regimes (Figure 2.1). These natural reefs were the closest extant reefs near Jensen Beach and Stuart in the IRL. This study and resulting Quick Assessment Guide focuses on these eastern oyster restoration projects.

Figure 2.1: Map of study sites labeled by site name. Green points signify natural reef locations, purple points signify artificial reef locations in the IRL, and blue points signify artificial reef locations in the SLE.

Table 2.2: Reef site information including reef code, reef name, reef type, waterbody, and location.

Reef site code	Reef site name	Reef type	Waterbody	Location
BERG	Bergalis reef	Artificial	IRL	Stuart, FL
DW	Driftwood reef	Artificial	IRL	Jensen Beach, FL
ES	Ellyn Stevenson reef	Artificial	SLE	Stuart, FL
FL	Flagler artificial reef	Artificial	SLE	Stuart, FL
FLN	Flagler natural reef	Natural	SLE	Stuart, FL

IRSP	Indian Riverside Park reef	Artificial	IRL	Jensen Beach, FL
JACK	Jack Island reef	Natural	IRL	Fort Pierce, FL
PEND	Pendarvis Park reef	Artificial	SLE	Palm City, FL
PENN	Pendarvis natural reef	Natural	SLE	Palm City, FL
ROSE	Roosevelt bridge reef	Natural	SLE	Stuart, FL
WC1	Wildcat 1 reef	Natural	IRL	Fort Pierce, FL
WC2	Wildcat 2 reef	Natural	IRL	Fort Pierce, FL

Figure 2.2: Photo of Florida Oceanographic Society volunteers and staff deploying an artificial oyster reef.

Table 2.3: List of ecological functions measured and permits acquired during summer 2025 sampling in the southern IRL and SLE.

Ecological functions measured	Permits acquired
Oyster reef development, persistence, and health	Florida Fish and Wildlife Special Activities License (SAL)
Shoreline protection	South Florida Water Management District (SFWMD) Verification of Exemption
Habitat provisioning	Florida Fish and Wildlife Special Activities License (SAL)

3.0 Oyster Settlement, Reef Development, and Persistence

3.1 Oyster Settlement

Settlement of spat (juvenile oysters) is essential for the formation and persistence of reef habitat. Spat settlement is determined by multiple factors including temperature, salinity, clarity of water, dissolved oxygen, currents, distance from natural reefs, presence of adult oysters, and reef roughness (rugosity) (Atwood & Grizzle, 2020; Baker & Mann, 1992; Bushek, 1988; Heilmayer et al., 2008; Hubbard & Reidenbach, 2015). Eastern oysters are broadcast spawners (they release their eggs and sperm into the water and fertilization occurs externally), with spawning cued by warm water temperatures (Wallace et al., 2008). Eastern oysters spend the first 14-20 days of life as planktonic larvae before settling out of the water column and attaching to the substrate as spat (Wallace et al., 2008). In the Indian River Lagoon, spawning can occur year round with highest settlement rates typically occurring in spring and fall, and lowest settlement rates in the coldest winter months (Wilson et al., 2005). In the southern Indian River Lagoon region, spat settlement spans a longer season and settlement rates are higher in the IRL compared to the SLE (Wilson et al., 2005).

3.1.1 Methodology

Spat settlement data was collected using spat Ts and oyster shell stringers (Phillips et al., 2023; Radabaugh et al., 2021). Three spat Ts made out of PVC pipe were deployed at each reef site (Figure 3). Spat Ts were made of 1/4in or 1in PVC depending on wave energy of site and availability of supplies. Two oyster shell stringers were hung on each spat T, with the oyster shell hung at intertidal elevation according to reef height. Stringers were composed of clean oyster shells approximately 3 inches in length acquired through Shuck and Share programs. Each stringer consisted of seven shells stacked on 14-gauge galvanized wire. New spat stringers were deployed at the beginning of each month and replaced at the end of each month, measuring spat recruitment May-August. After collection, stringers were brought to the lab for processing. For each stringer, spat observed on the interior shell side of the middle five shells was enumerated. A picture was taken of the third shell interior for reference (Phillips et al., 2023). More detailed information about spat recruitment methodology can be found in the document appendices: Appendix A - *Spat Monitoring SOP*.

Figure 3.1: Spat T deployed at WC1 reef site in the IRL.

3.1.2 Results

Spat settlement in the southern IRL and SLE appears to vary both spatially and temporally across waterbodies and months. Spat settlement in the SLE declined throughout the summer months with the highest average spat per shell counts in May (mean 22.53 ± 1.58) and lowest in August (mean 1.13 ± 0.14). In the IRL, spat settlement peaked mid-summer with lowest settlement in May (mean 1.64 ± 0.20), increasing through June, peaking in July (mean 17.52 ± 1.44) and declining again in August (Figure 3.1).

When comparing natural and artificial reefs in the region, artificial reefs experienced higher spat settlement every summer month except for May. Across the four summer months sampled, natural reefs averaged 5.20 ± 0.47 spat per shell, while artificial reefs averaged 15.87 ± 0.62 spat per shell (Figure 3.3).

As expected, spat settlement varies spatially and temporally depending on waterbody and month; however, spat settlement patterns regarding reef type are surprising. We did not expect to see large differences between natural and artificial sites and did not expect artificial reefs to outperform natural reefs in spat settlement. Analyzing spat settlement data in conjunction with size class frequency data reveals that artificial reef sites are likely receiving adequate spat settlement; however, a majority of spat are not surviving to reproductive size.

Figure 3.2: Line graph showing average number of spat per shell with standard error by reef type over the summer months in 2025.

Figure 3.3: Line graph showing average number of spat per shell with standard error by waterbody over the summer months in 2025.

Figure 3.4: Boxplots of total spat per shell by site during four months of monitoring with colors distinguishing artificial and natural reefs.

Our study has revealed surprising patterns in spat settlement between natural and artificial reefs in the southern IRL and SLE (Figure 3.4). Although we feel these patterns warrant further investigation and are insightful in understanding size class frequency results, spat settlement is not considered a universal monitoring metric (Baggett et al., 2014; Birch et al., 2025) as collecting spat data is time and resource intensive. Spat settlement is a highly important metric for artificial reef site selection; however, collecting percent cover, density, and size class frequency data should be prioritized in long-term monitoring protocols.

3.2 Reef Development

Reef development metrics are the most important markers of reef health and success, and can be described quickly and easily using quadrat sampling for percent cover, density of live oyster, and size class frequency distributions. Percent cover, density of live oyster, and size class frequency measurements are considered universal metrics that should be measured for every artificial oyster reef project (L. Baggett, 2014; Birch et al., 2025). Oyster growth rate and survival is affected by a variety of environmental factors including temperature, salinity, food availability, and turbidity, as well as predation and direct human impacts (Dekshenieks et al., 1993; Hofmann et al., 1994).

Percent cover measurements reflect overall reef structure and health, describing the composition of the reef surface (Janiak et al., 2021). Healthy oyster reefs should have high percent cover of live oyster compared to shell-cultch and sediment.

Density measurements describe the number of live oysters per sampling unit, which can be extrapolated using reef area to calculate live oyster coverage for a reef site (L. Baggett, 2014; Janiak et al., 2021). A high number of live oyster per square meter indicates a healthy reef, with 50 live oysters per square meter established as the minimum requirement for restoration success in the region (M. Anderson, personal communication, October 25, 2025). Due to the devastating impact of freshwater releases from 2005-2018, mean oyster densities vary greatly in the SLE across years, ranging from 2 oysters per square meter to 2000 oysters per square meter (Parker & Radigan, 2020).

Size class frequency distributions describe oyster population composition, survivorship, and growth, shedding light on oyster population structure of the reef (L. Baggett, 2014; Janiak et al., 2021). Healthy oyster reefs should be composed of a range of size classes, with many new recruits and many reproductive-size individuals. *Crassostrea virginica* usually begin spawning at 40-50mm in length, with a harvest size of 76mm in length (Hansen et al., 2024; Hofmann et al., 1994). In the central SLE, from 2005-2018 the mean shell height of adult oysters was found to be 42mm (Parker & Radigan, 2020). Although harvesting is not permitted in the southern IRL or SLE, adult oysters of harvest size can be difficult to find on some oyster reef sites in the southern IRL.

Other species of bivalve are found in the region including the flat tree oyster (*Isonogmon alatus*) and crested oyster (*Ostrea equestris*). These bivalves are especially common on high salinity reef sites (Galtsoff & Merrill, 1962; Hoese, 1960; Markwith, 2010). Restoration initiatives tend to focus on the eastern oyster (*Crassostrea virginica*) due to the species's reef building capacity and associated ecosystem services; however, other bivalve species can be abundant on reefs. Flat tree oysters and crested oysters are not reef building species, and the recruitment of these species to reef sites can have implications for reef structure and size class frequency data. Flat tree oysters and crested oysters do not typically coalesce to build reefs; therefore, if artificial reefs are largely composed of flat tree oysters or crested oysters, the reef may not coalesce and grow as expected. Crested oysters are commonly mistaken for young eastern oysters, as the maximum adult size for crested oysters is 40mm (Galtsoff & Merrill, 1962; Markwith, 2010). If a reef has high densities of crested oysters, practitioners may be misled to think eastern oysters at the reef site are not reaching adult size when the reef is primarily composed of crested oysters.

3.2.1 Methodology

To quantify percent cover, density of live oyster, and oyster size class frequency distribution, random quadrat sampling was used across twelve reef study sites. Random sampling

was conducted for each parameter by superimposing a numbered grid on reef site diagrams and using a random number generator to determine eight locations to be sampled with a 1m² quadrat (Baggett et al., 2014). Random sampling methodology was chosen due to the variability in reef shape and size between natural and artificial reef sites. For projects focused on reefs of similar size and shape, different sampling methodologies may be more applicable (Birch et al., 2025; Janiak, 2021). This study focuses on intertidal reef habitat; therefore, only areas of natural and artificial reef that are exposed at negative low tides were sampled to adhere to project scope and practical feasibility (L. Baggett, 2014; Cole, 2023; Hansen et al., 2024; Janiak et al., 2021). More detailed information regarding these methodologies can be found in the Appendix B - Reef Monitoring SOP.

Percent cover was quantified using the point-intercept method outlined by Janiak (2021). Sampling was conducted using 1m² grid quadrats. A 1m² grid quadrat contains strings placed every 10cm vertically and horizontally, creating 81 string crossings (Figure 3.4). Grid quadrats are laid on the reef surface and substrate underneath each cross-string is tallied into different categories: live eastern oyster, boxed oyster, shell-culch, sediment, and other. This approach was repeated in eight random locations per reef, utilizing the random sampling methodology described previously.

Figure 3.4: Researcher collecting percent cover data using a 1m² grid quadrat.

Density of live oyster was determined by counting the number of live oysters on the surface of the reef within six 1/4m² quadrats. Density and size class frequency measures are typically determined through reef excavations or removing bags of shell from artificial reef sites; however, due to the fragility and health of oyster reefs within our study area, we quantified the

number of live oysters on the reef surface within 1/4m² quadrats instead of excavating reef material. Every live oyster over 10mm in shell height was counted on the surface of the reef within the quadrat area without moving oyster clumps (Figure 3.5). Density of live oyster measurements were taken following percent cover measurements for the first six random locations generated by the random number generator at each reef.

Sampling for oyster size class frequency occurred concurrently with density of live oyster. For the first 50 oysters counted within the 1/4m² quadrats, the shell height of each live oyster was measured to the nearest millimeter with a pair of calipers (Figure 3.5). Shell height was measured from the umbo to the furthest extent of the shell. Only oysters greater than 10mm were measured to accurately capture size frequencies of adult oysters and avoid skewing data by counting newly settled larvae and young recruits. The first 50 live oysters within the quadrat were measured to ensure a robust sample size while balancing practicality (L. Baggett, 2014). During analysis, recorded oyster shell heights were grouped into 5 size class bins: 10-25mm (recruits), 26-40mm (subadult), 41-75mm (reproductive adult), >75mm (market size adult) (L. Baggett, 2014; Hansen et al., 2024).

Figure 3.5: 1/4m² quadrat and calipers used to collect live oyster density and size class frequency data.

Flat tree oysters can be distinguished from eastern oysters in the field; therefore, presence of flat tree oysters were recorded during percent cover, density of live oyster, and size class frequency measurements, described in more detail in Appendix B - Reef Monitoring SOP. Crested oysters and eastern oysters are difficult to differentiate in the field, since the most reliable distinguishing character occurs on the interior margin of the oyster shells. To estimate the proportion of reef composed of crested oysters, a sample size of approximately 15 boxed (recently deceased) oysters were sampled to be identified at the lab (Figure 3.6). Boxed oysters

ranging from 10-40mm were opportunistically sampled from all reef sites, as crested oysters typically grow to a maximum of 40mm in shell height. More detailed methodology can be found in Appendix B - Reef Monitoring SOP.

Figure 3.6: (Left) *Crassostrea virginica* boxed oysters post-processing. (Right) *Ostrea equestris* boxed oyster post-processing.

3.2.2. Results

Percent Cover

Reef composition

Figure 3.7: Reef composition of substrates by reef type. Cool colors denote living reef substrate and warm colors denote non-living substrate.

Substrate composition of natural and artificial reefs in the southern IRL and SLE varies across sites, with comparison of natural and artificial reefs showing similar composition. Natural reefs are composed of slightly higher proportions of live eastern oyster than artificial reefs. Mean percent cover of live eastern oysters on natural reefs is 8.98 ± 1.52 ; while percent cover of live eastern oysters on artificial reefs is 6.48 ± 1.15 . Both natural and artificial reefs are primarily composed of shell-cultch. According to our percent cover data, artificial and natural reefs show similar substrate composition (Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.8: Reef composition of substrates by reef site with artificial reef sites listed left of the bold line and natural reefs on the right. Cool colors denote living reef substrate and warm colors denote non-living substrate.

Figure 3.9: Percentage of substrate sampled covered with plastic restoration material by artificial reef site.

As artificial reefs mature, plastic cover is expected to decline as live oyster cover increases. This general trend can be seen when analyzing percent cover of live oyster compared to percent cover of plastic material. Since greater live oyster cover coincides with reduced plastic visibility, plastic percent cover serves as a simple and practical visual indicator of reef health and progression (Figure 3.9).

Percent cover is a very simple and practical methodology to rapidly assess oyster reef status, as shown in this study. Utilizing percent cover to attain reef composition information paints a picture of the reef substrate as a whole, providing proportions of living reef substrate to non-living shell or sediment. Density and size class frequency data is important to shed light on the status of the eastern oyster population of a reef site, while percent cover provides a broader perspective of reef composition. We strongly recommend implementing percent cover monitoring in long-term quick assessment of oyster reef sites.

Density of live oysters

Similar to the pattern discovered by percent cover measurements, density of live oyster varies across sites, with comparison of natural and artificial reefs showing similar densities. Mean density of live eastern oysters is slightly higher on artificial reefs (77.67 ± 15.72); while mean density of live eastern oysters on natural reefs is 60.89 ± 12.80 . Median density of live oyster for artificial reefs is slightly lower (24.0) than natural reefs (26.0). Overall, natural and artificial reefs show similar density of live oyster, with some reefs having high density and some reefs having a low density (Figure 3.10).

Figure 3.10: Density of live eastern oyster per meter squared by reef site.

Figure 3.11: Density of live eastern oyster per square meter by reef type.

Our study has shown density to be a helpful measurement in better understanding reef composition and health. For example, we can see that the BERG reef is not meeting live density means for both artificial and natural reefs (Figure 3.10). Density data compliments percent cover data, focusing on the vital metric of live eastern oysters. Density and size class are two meaningful metrics that are collected together; therefore, we highly recommend practitioners collect density data when monitoring aging reef restoration projects.

Size class frequency distribution

Figure 3.12: Frequency of size classes by reef type. Size classes include spat (0-10mm), recruits (11-25mm), subadults (26-40mm), adults (41-75mm), and harvest size (>75mm).

Figure 3.13: Percent composition of size classes by reef type. Size classes include spat (0-10mm), recruits (11-25mm), subadults (26-40mm), adults (41-75mm), and harvest size (>75mm).

Artificial reefs have higher numbers of small oysters (recruits and subadults), while natural reefs have higher numbers of reproductive individuals (adults and harvest; Figures 3.12 and 3.13). While previous analysis of density of live oyster and percent cover show that artificial and natural reefs are similar, the differences in size class frequency distributions show that there may still be differences in structure between the two reef types. The mean number of recruit size oysters (11-25mm) was much higher on artificial reefs (47.50 ± 22.22) compared to natural reefs (8.17 ± 1.96). While the mean number of adult size oysters (41-75mm) was much higher on natural reefs (52.00 ± 20.91) than artificial reefs (29.33 ± 14.45). When analyzing medians to mitigate the influence of outliers, the pattern remains for both recruit size oysters (artificial: 24.0, natural: 7.5) and adult size oysters (artificial: 11.0, natural: 35.0). Since all artificial reefs are over six years in age, we do not expect reef age to be a strong contributing factor to difference in size class distribution as it is for newly established man-made reefs. Instead, we propose this difference in size class composition could be due to mortality of younger oysters before individuals can reach reproductive size on artificial reefs.

Results from this study suggest that collecting data for size class frequency is of vital importance to understanding artificial reef health and structure. The size class frequency data collected in this study shines light on differences in reef structure between natural and aging

artificial reefs which would have been missed if percent cover and density data had been collected alone. The results from our size frequency data leads to questions about which factors could lead to higher mortality rates of recruits and subadult oysters on artificial reefs in the southern IRL and SLE.

Oyster species composition

Figure 3.14: Proportion of *Crassostrea virginica* and *Isognomon alatus* for each reef site based on density data.

Figure 3.15: Proportion of *Crassostrea virginica* and *Ostrea equestris* for each reef site based on density data.

Substrate composition of oyster species and species density varied between sites in the southern IRL and SLE. As expected, IRL sites (higher salinity) supported a greater presence of *Ostrea equestris* and *Isognomon alatus*, while SLE sites (lower salinity) were dominated by *Crassostrea virginica* (Figures 3.14 and 3.15).

Species counts showed that *C. virginica* was present across all reefs, with particularly high totals at ES (19), PEND (16), and ROSE (18). In contrast, *O. equestris* was more abundant at BERG (14), WC1 (13), and WC2 (6), with little to no presence at lower salinity SLE sites. This pattern reflects the salinity tolerance of *O. equestris*, favoring the more marine conditions of the IRL. Density analysis reinforces these patterns. Total counts of eastern oysters were highest at ROSE (252), PEND (248), and ES (228), while IRL sites such as BERG (3) and IRSP (19) supported lower densities overall. Flat tree oysters were present in smaller numbers, but they reached their highest densities at WC2 (29) and WC1 (15), both in higher-salinity IRL waters.

When comparing reef sites, SLE reefs generally supported higher eastern oyster densities, consistent with the species' adaptation to brackish conditions. In contrast, IRL reefs supported a more diverse mix of bivalve species, particularly with higher proportions of crested oysters and

flat tree oysters. When conducting evaluating the success of artificial reef sites in high salinity waterbodies, practitioners should sample for crested oyster and flat tree oyster percent cover and densities to better understand patterns of reef dynamics and coalescence that impact reef restoration success. It may also be an indicator of salinity in the system.

4.0 Reef Persistence

Multiple factors affect reef persistence including reef area, reef height, submergence time, and reef rugosity. Reef area and reef height are considered universal metrics that should be measured for every artificial oyster reef project (L. Baggett, 2014). Reef area and height parameters are especially helpful in long-term oyster reef monitoring as they are relatively stable over multiple years (unless there is a large storm event, i.e. hurricane) (Janiak et al., 2021). Meanwhile, measuring rugosity using the chain-and-tape method is a quick and easy way to assess reef complexity, an important measurement that can change on relatively short timescales (Janiak et al., 2021).

Reef area is an important parameter that can be used to estimate the impact of existing natural and artificial reef projects. Reef area is the aerial extent of the reef site, including the areas of all reef patches (L. Baggett, 2014). Determining reef area is crucial to understanding reef size, extrapolating reef density and composition metrics for the site, and estimating impacts of ecosystem services (L. Baggett, 2014). For example, live oyster density and percent cover data can be extrapolated using reef area measurements to better understand oyster population and overall site health. Reef area is an important measure to better understand population health and resilience.

Reef height is an important determining factor in restored reef persistence, with taller reef heights protecting the reef from sedimentation and disarticulation (Colden et al., 2017; Housego & Rosman, 2016; Jordan-Cooley et al., 2011). Reefs can either outpace sedimentation via oyster growth, become buried as sediment deposition outpaces oyster growth, or reach a steady state of height determined by a balance of sedimentation and oyster growth (Housego & Rosman, 2016). Longer reef inundation times can foster increased oyster growth rates; however, long submergence times can lead to increased oyster predator interactions (Colden et al., 2017; Jordan-Cooley et al., 2011; Morris et al., 2021; Scyphers et al., 2011). In artificial reef design, inundation time must be balanced with reef height to ensure reefs are at appropriate heights for oyster growth and persistence, as well as wave abatement and sediment attenuation. Reef height measurements in combination with observed submergence times can provide a snapshot measurement of changes in reef structure over time (growth vs subsidence), potential ecosystem services (wave abatement vs submerged aquatic resources), and predator-prey interactions (intertidal vs subtidal foodwebs and predator abundance) (L. Baggett, 2014). Artificial oyster reefs in the southern IRL and SLE were originally constructed to heights of approximately 0.5m above the surrounding sediment (V. Encomio, personal communication, July 16, 2024).

Reef rugosity describes the surface complexity of reef structures. For oyster reefs, high reef rugosity reflects high abundance of live oysters, lends to increased spat recruitment, and

provides vital habitat through increased availability of interstitial space (D. J. Cannon et al., 2023; Hubbard & Reidenbach, 2015). In Mosquito Lagoon (the farthest northern extent of the IRL system), restored reefs have been shown to reach similar rugosities as natural reefs within 4 years (D. Cannon et al., 2022).

4.1.1 Methodology

Reef persistence was monitored using a Trimble handheld GPS unit to collect data for reef area, string and level methodology to determine reef height, and the chain-tape method to measure reef rugosity. More detailed information regarding these methodologies can be found in the Appendix B - Reef Monitoring SOP.

Reef area data was collected using a Trimble handheld GPS unit. The Trimble GPS was used to create aerial polygons by collecting point coordinates at 1 second intervals along the entire reef edge. The reef edge was defined as the area along the edge of the reef where oyster shell-cultch makes up 25% or less of the substrate and the majority of substrate has transitioned to sediment (L. Baggett, 2014; Janiak et al., 2021). For reef sites made up of multiple patches or modules, point coordinates were collected along the reef edge for each patch or module. Spatial data collected by the Trimble GPS unit was corrected in GPS Pathfinder and mapped in ArcGIS Pro. The goal of this research is to provide accessible methodologies for practitioners, and collection and analysis of spatial data using handheld GPS and spatial analysis software (ArcGIS) is common in natural resource management; however, not all practitioners have GPS capable equipment and spatial data experience. In these situations, practitioners can still estimate reef area by measuring reef length and width with transect tape (Janiak et al., 2021).

Submergence time was not explicitly quantified; however, through repeated sampling events researchers were able to categorize reef modules or patches as well as entire sites as intertidal, mostly submerged, or always submerged (Figure 4.3). Submergence time is important to consider when analyzing data, and knowledge regarding inundation time can be acquired over time during fieldwork sampling.

Reef height was determined by taking four reef height measurements across the crest of the reef site (Figure 4.1). The reef site was visually assessed to identify four of the highest points spread out across the site. A string was held against the identified highest point and walked out to the offshore reef edge (edge of the reef where oyster shell-cultch makes up 25% or less of the substrate and the majority of substrate has transitioned to sediment). A stadia rod was placed at the reef edge, and the string was held next to the stadia rod. Then a line level was attached to the string, and the string was adjusted vertically along the stadia rod until the line level was straight and the height on the stadia rod was recorded to the nearest 0.25inch. This measurement was repeated at the four high points identified across the reef site. Reef height can also be sampled

using other spatial data collection methods such as Trimble Handheld GPS, RTK, and laser level; however, our research employed the string level methodology as a simple, accessible, and cost-effective method.

Figure 4.1: Researchers measuring reef height using the string and level methodology.

Reef rugosity was measured using the chain and tape method described in Janiak et al. (2021) at the eight 1m^2 quadrats sampled for percent cover (Figure 4.2). A stainless steel ball chain (1m length, 2mm ball width) was laid across the substrate, contouring to the substrate. Transect tape was laid in a straight line alongside the chain. Rugosity index is calculated as the difference in chain-laid distance and fixed distance (1m) to provide eight rugosity measurements per reef.

Figure 4.2: Diagram depicting rugosity measurement using chain and tape method from Janiak et al., 2021.

4.1.2 Results

Reef area and submergence

Figure 4.3 (Left) GIS map of reef area at ROSE reef. The large white polygon is the total reef area and the smaller white polygon is the area of reef exposed on a typical low tide; (Right) GIS map of reef area at BERG reef. Black polygons are reef modules that are exposed during negative low tides and blue polygons are modules that are only exposed at the most extreme negative low tides.

While submergence time was not specifically quantified during this study, it can be relatively inferred through reef height data and field observation. Like reef height, submergence time is an important metric to understand reef dynamics such as interspecies competition and predation rates. For example, the BERG artificial reef site has the lowest average reef height (18.89cm) and several of the modules were only observed exposed at the strongest negative low tides, implying areas of the BERG reef have relatively longer submergence times when compared within and across sites (Figure 4.3).

Reef height

In the southern IRL and SLE, natural reefs are found to have taller reef heights than artificial reefs (Figures 4.4 and 4.5). The mean height for natural reefs is $59.19\text{cm} \pm 4.2$, while mean height for artificial reefs is $34.58\text{cm} \pm 2.28$. Artificial reefs in the region were built to approximately 50cm in height. Increase in reef height is considered a universal metric to understand artificial reef success, with successful reefs increasing in height (L. Baggett, 2014). According to our data, artificial reefs in the region are often decreasing in reef height and although these artificial reefs are considered aging, the established reefs do not reflect the heights of nearby natural reefs.

Figure 4.4: Average reef height by site with standard error.

Figure 4.5: Boxplots of reef height measurements by reef type.

Results from this study suggest collecting reef height data is helpful in determining reef persistence, especially when compared to original deployment height and/or surrounding natural reef heights. Reef height data is not a standalone metric of reef health and success; however, this quick and easy measurement can be used in conjunction with other metrics to better understand reef dynamics.

Rugosity

Figure 4.6: Rugosity index by reef site (scale of 0-1, with 1 being no measurable complexity).

Figure 4.7: Rugosity index by reef type (scale of 0-1, with 1 being no measurable complexity).

Rugosity indices fall on a scale of 0-1, with 1 being no measurable complexity. As the rugosity indices approaches zero, the substrate is increasingly rugose. Rugosity of natural and artificial reefs in the southern IRL and SLE was similar across sites, with comparison of natural and artificial reefs showing very similar rugosity statistics (Figures 4.6 and 4.7). Mean rugosity of natural and artificial reefs were determined to be the same (0.83m), and median rugosity only varied slightly (artificial: 0.84, natural: 0.86). Similar rugosity indices found across natural and artificial reef sites align with similarity in percent cover and density of live oyster measurements.

Rugosity index has not been previously identified as a universal metric; however, our study has shown it to be helpful complimentary data (L. Baggett, 2014). Since rugosity measurements are easy to collect and the equipment is very cost-effective, we recommend practitioners collect rugosity data if feasible.

5.0 Oyster Health

While oyster reefs play a major ecological role in their estuarine ecosystems, populations have been declining due to multiple stressors including habitat loss and degradation, overharvesting, and disease (Mackenzie, 2007; Wilberg et al., 2011). For oysters to successfully contribute to these important ecological roles, the overall health of living oysters needs to be considered. Sampling for condition index and prevalence and intensity of Dermo disease (*Perkinsus marinus*) can provide insights to oyster health in the IRL region and across reef sites.

5.1 Condition Index

An assessment of oyster reef health using a condition index rating key for individual oyster tissue was developed by Quick & Mackin (1971), and has since been implemented by Kim et al. (2006) in a NOAA Technical Memorandum. This condition index rating key scores oyster tissue from 1-9, with 1 indicating that oyster health is very good and 9 indicating oyster health is very poor (Table 5.1). This assessment is relatively simple, and can provide baseline information about the physical state of an individual oyster.

Table 5.1: Condition Index Rating Key

#	<i>Oyster Appearance</i>
1	Animal firm and filling shell cavity; coloration creamy white and evenly textured, usually ready to spawn.
2	Not quite as firm or large as above; usually ready to spawn.
3	Coloration is less opaque, often slightly yellow or gray.
4	Animal distinctly not filling shell cavity; coloration often mottled, with blood vessels and muscle fibers showing through the more translucent epithelium.
5	Oyster well-developed but not opaque or tending toward white; grayish and translucent; flesh flaccid.
6	Translucency is more pronounced.
7	Oyster not well-developed, darker gray, often greenish; pericardial cavity clear; small portion of shell cavity filled.
8	Negative qualities are more accentuated.

9	Animal distinctly atrophied; coloration dark and uneven, very translucent; seldom more than a third of shell cavity occupied; adductor muscle often discolored and transparent even in the normally white sector.
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However, a more quantitative assessment of oyster health includes using the condition index (CI) as a metric. CI is used for assessing the quality of bivalves (e.g., Zeng & Yang, 2021) and has been widely implemented for analyzing the condition of various oyster species (Rebelo et al., 2005; Walton et al., 2013). In particular, this metric assesses the quality of oysters by determining tissue fullness relative to the size of the shell (Lawrence & Scott, 1982). Although various methods for CI have been explored and documented in the literature, we calculated CI by using Hopkin’s formula (Equation 1; Hopkins, 1949; Lawrence & Scott, 1982; Rainer & Mann, 1992).

Equation 1

$$CI = \frac{\text{dry tissue weight (g)} \times 100}{\text{whole oyster weight (g)} - \text{dry shell weight (g)}}$$

In general, a higher CI value indicates that the tissue occupies a greater portion of the shell cavity, while a lower CI value suggests less tissue relative to shell size (Mann, 1978). CI values can be affected by a multitude of factors such as the availability of food, reproductive state the organism is in, or pollution found in the water column to name a few (Manley & Walker, 2011; Dumbauld et al., 2023). A study by Mercado-Silva (2005) found that the CI of eastern oysters was significantly higher in larger systems (i.e., rivers) than in lower flux systems (i.e., creeks), and that the presence of parasites (i.e., pea crabs) dramatically reduced CI values. Although this particular CI metric provides accurate and valuable insights into tissue fullness relative to bivalve size, it is more difficult to implement due to its reliance on a drying process that must be done in a lab setting, making it more time-consuming and potentially costly.

5.1.1 Methodology

To assess oyster health, approximately 15 individuals were collected from 11 sites across two regions (SLE and IRL) and two site types (natural and restored) for a total of n = 162. Oyster collection began in August 2025, which coincided with the lowest tidal levels to ensure full visibility and access to all oyster reefs. Oysters from each individual site were placed into labeled mesh bags and stored in a cooler that was lined with ice packs, which were covered by towels to help maintain an optimal temperature and ensure survival throughout the transportation process. At sites where collecting 15 oysters was not feasible due to reef quality, as many individuals as conditions allowed were collected. The target size chosen for this particular study was the 41-75mm size class, which includes the reproductive adults, as they have been observed across all 11 oyster reefs (Baggett et al. 2015, pers. obv Emily Surmont). Oysters were not collected from the

BERG artificial reef site, as the population of adult oysters in the designated size class is extremely limited. After collection, oysters were transported to Florida Oceanographic Society for processing. Once brought into the laboratory, oysters from the same site were cleaned of any removable organisms (e.g., algae) and placed onto a dedicated tray in the cooler that was labeled by site to ensure proper sample identification. Individual oysters were then placed on a tray with an individual identification tag and ruler. Two photographs were then taken: the first photograph captured the shell length and height (Figure 5.1- A) and the second photograph captured the shell width (Figure 5.1- B). All measurement analyses for shell length, height, and width were conducted using ImageJ (Schneider et al., 2012).

Figure 5.1: Photographs capturing (A) shell length, height, and (B) width.

After photographs were taken, the oyster was weighed. This step in particular is essential as it provides one of the required values (i.e., whole oyster wet weight (g)) in the CI equation (Equation 1). However, it's important to note that the weight of individual oysters may be misleading if other organisms (e.g., barnacles) are attached or if the oyster is anchored to another surface (e.g., another oyster). Therefore, we excluded any individuals whose weight did not represent their true whole oyster wet weight when conducting the CI metric.

Once weighed, individual oysters were shucked open, and a photograph of the oyster tissue was taken to determine the physical state of the oyster tissue using the Quick & Mackin (1971) condition index rating key (Table 5.1; Figure 5.2).

A small sample of tissue (~5mm) was then excised from each oyster for disease analysis (refer to 5.2 and Appendix D for further information). The remainder of tissue from each oyster was removed, patted dry with a paper towel, and placed on individually labeled aluminum pans and into a drying oven at 68°C for 24 hours. In addition to drying the tissue, oyster shells were placed on a tray and dried overnight at room temperature. After 24 hours, the weight of the dry tissue and dry shell were taken, both of which are required values for the CI equation (Equation 1). More detailed, step-by-step methodology can be found in Appendix C- Condition Index SOP.

Figure 5.2: Photograph capturing oyster tissue.

5.1.2 Results

Based on the oyster condition rating index developed by Quick & Mackin (1971), the lower the rating the better the oyster physical state. When oysters were grouped by site type (i.e., natural and restored), the state of natural oysters ($n = 80$; 3.05 ± 0.16) was slightly better than those of restored oysters ($n = 73$; 3.45 ± 0.19) (Figure 5.3).

Figure 5.3: Condition index rating key (Quick & Mackin, 1971) where 1 indicates the physical state of an oyster is very good and 9 indicates the physical state is very poor, based on site type (natural and restored).

When grouped by site type and waterbody (i.e., IRL and SLE), natural and restored oysters from SLE showed almost no difference in the mean condition index rating (Table 5.2). However, there was a larger decrease in the physical state of oysters from restored reefs in the IRL (Table 2; Figure 5.4).

Table 5.2. Mean and standard error of condition index rating key for oysters grouped by site type and region.

Site Type	Region	Count	Mean	SE
Natural	IRL	41	2.70	0.18
Natural	SLE	39	3.42	0.26
Restored	IRL	30	3.25	0.27
Restored	SLE	43	3.60	0.25

Figure 5.4: Condition index rating key (Quick & Mackin, 1971) where 1 indicates the physical state of an oyster is very good and 9 indicates the physical state is very poor, based on site type (natural and restored) and region (IRL and SLE) with standard error bars.

While a lower value of the oyster condition rating index developed by Quick & Mackin (1971) is more ideal, the opposite is true for CI values. In particular, a higher CI value indicates the oyster is occupying a greater portion of the shell cavity (Mann, 1978). When grouped by site type, natural oysters had a slightly higher CI value (3.85 ± 0.38) compared to restored oysters (3.48 ± 0.21 ; Figure 5.5).

Figure 5.5: Condition index for sites based on site type (natural and restored) with standard error bars.

However, when looking at the data grouped by site type and region we see that across both the IRL and SLE, the CI values for natural areas are higher than for restored areas. Indeed, the IRL region has higher CI values for both natural and restored when compared to the SLE (Table 5.3; Figure 5.6).

Table 5.3: Mean and standard error of condition index for oysters grouped by site type and region.

Site Type	Region	Count	Mean	SE
Natural	IRL	23	4.79	0.23
Natural	SLE	21	2.82	0.69
Restored	IRL	27	4.42	0.20
Restored	SLE	24	2.42	0.25

Figure 5.6: Condition index for sites based on site type (natural and restored) and region (IRL and SLE) with standard error bars.

In the southern IRL and SLE slight differences were detected across reef types and waterbodies. Overall, natural reefs were found to have slightly healthier CI metrics than restored reefs, and reef sites in the IRL were found to have healthier CI metrics than reefs in SLE. Regardless of the method implemented (i.e., Quick and Mackin rating key or Hopkin’s formula), the results followed the same pattern.

Although CI is not considered a required monitoring metric (Birch et al., 2025; L. Baggett, 2014), we found that collecting CI can be a practical way for practitioners to shed light on physical oyster health when sampled in conjunction with other reef development and persistence metrics. The Quick and Mackin protocol does not require special laboratory equipment (and makes measuring CI increasingly feasible).

5.2 Disease

Disease is a significant stressor to oyster reef health (King et al., 2015). In particular, *Perkinsus marinus*, a protozoan parasite responsible for causing dermo disease, has caused widespread mortality among oyster populations along the eastern coast of the United States (Ewart & Ford, 1993). Our study quantified prevalence and intensity of dermo disease to better understand the impacts of disease on aging artificial and natural reefs in the region.

5.2.1 Methodology

To assess disease prevalence, tissue samples were collected from the oysters that were being analyzed for condition index. For a detailed description of the collection and processing procedures, see Section 5.1.1 Methodology and Appendix C- Condition Index SOP for more details. From each oyster, a small piece of mantle-edge tissue was excised and placed into a 15 mL culture tube containing 5 mL of Ray's Fluid Thioglycolate Medium (RFTM) and 0.5 mL of the antibiotic solution. Each culture tube was inverted to ensure the tissue sample was fully submerged in the RFTM and then placed in dark conditions at room temperature for 5 days. After the incubation period, the tissue was removed from the RFTM and placed onto a microscope slide. Individual tissue samples were carefully teased apart and stained with 1-2 drops of Lugol's iodine solution to enhance hyphospore contrast and mounted with a cover slip for microscopic examination. For a detailed step-by-step assay protocol, refer to Appendix D.

Using a Leica MDG41 dissection microscope, each tissue sample was carefully examined. To capture the area of each sample, a photograph was taken with a ruler placed in frame and analyzed using the area function in ImageJ (Schneider et al., 2012; Figure 5.7).

Figure 5.7: *Photograph capturing tissue sample.*

If no hyphospores were observed, the sample was assigned a prevalence score of 0. If hyphospores were present, the tissue was assigned a score of 1, and all visible hyphospores were counted (Figure 5.8). In cases where hyphospore counts exceeded 300 within approximately 25% of the total tissue area, five random 1 mm² (5 mm² total) subsamples were taken for quantification using the grid function in ImageJ (Schneider et al., 2012; Figure 5.9).

Figure 5.8: Photograph capturing tissue sample with hypnozoites present.

Figure 5.9: Photograph capturing tissue sample that was subsampled due to the large amount of hypnozoites present; five 1 mm² (5 mm² total) squares were subsampled for quantification.

In addition to counting the hypnozoites and quantifying the density, each tissue sample was assigned a number from the semi-quantitative infection intensity scale (Table 5.4).

Table 5.4: Semi-quantitative scale of infection intensity.

<i>Infection_Intensity</i>	<i>Description</i>
0.00	No hyphospores present.
0.33	1-10 hyphospores.
0.67	11-74 hyphospores.
1.00	75-125 hyphospores.
1.33	>125 hyphospores but <25% of tissue is hyphospores.
1.67	<25% of tissue is hyphospores.
2.00	25% of tissue is hyphospores.
2.33	>25% but way less <50% of tissue is hyphospores.
2.67	>25% but <50% of tissue is hyphospores.
3.00	50% of tissue is hyphospores.
3.33	>50% but way less <75% of tissue is hyphospores.
3.67	>50% but <75% of tissue is hyphospores.
4.00	75% of tissue is hyphospores.
4.33	>75% but way <100% of tissue is hyphospores.
4.67	>75% of tissue is hyphospores but some tissue is still visible.
5.00	Nearly 100% of tissue is hyphospores.

5.2.2 Results

Out of the 11 sites sampled, only 1 natural site in the SLE was found without the presence of any hyphospores (i.e., PENN) in our tissue samples. Grouped by site type, the proportion of individuals that were infected (≥ 1 hyphospore present) were higher in restored than natural reefs (Figure 5.10).

Figure 5.10: *Proportion of individuals infected based on site type.*

Even though the CI values of the IRL natural and restored oysters were overall higher (see Section 5.1.2 Results, Figure 5.6), both IRL natural and restored oysters had higher proportions of individuals infected than those of SLE (Figure 5.11).

Figure 5.11: Proportion of individuals infected based on site type and region.

Restored oyster reefs also exhibited higher densities of hyphospores per mm², with an average of 0.87 ± 0.36 hyphospores for natural ($n = 81$) versus 2.62 ± 1.06 for restored ($n = 75$; Figure 12).

Figure 5.12: Density of hypospores per mm² based on site type (natural and restored) with standard error bars.

It may be crucial to take into account regions that have different biological significance. Here, we see that individuals from the IRL are the ones who are mostly contributing to the density of hypospores present (Figure 5.13, Table 5.5).

Figure 5.13: Density of hyphospores per mm² based on site type (natural and restored) and region (IRL and SLE) with standard error bars.

Table 5.5: Mean and standard error of condition index for oysters grouped by site type and region.

Site Type	Count	Region	Mean	SE
Natural	40	IRL	1.70	0.71
Natural	41	SLE	0.05	0.02
Restored	30	IRL	6.20	2.54
Restored	46	SLE	0.23	0.10

Figure 5.14: Infection intensity based on the semi-quantitative scale (Table 3) with standard error bars.

Figure 5.15: Infection intensity based on the semi-quantitative scale (Table 3) with standard error bars.

As expected, prevalence and intensity of dermo disease was found to be higher in the southern IRL versus the SLE, as IRL sites experience consistently high salinities compared to SLE sites (Figure 5.15). Interestingly, restored reefs were also found to have higher prevalence and intensity of dermo disease across waterbodies (Figure 5.14).

Sampling for dermo disease is not considered a universal monitoring metric (Birch et al., 2025; L. Baggett, 2014), and is not always feasible as institutional laboratory equipment and experience is required. Therefore, we recommend practitioners sample for oyster disease utilising these protocols if reef sites exist in an environment with consistently high temperatures and salinities, if disease is suspected as a driver of population decline, or if interested specifically in disease evaluation.

6.0 Shoreline Protection

6.1 Wave Attenuation

In the context of climate change, physical threats to coastal property have increased the need for storm surge protection and erosion control. Nature-based Solutions (NbS) are coastal management methods that use natural systems like oyster reefs, mangroves, or saltmarshes, to protect shoreline and provide additional economic and cultural benefits. Among these systems, oyster reefs are an increasingly popular method for buffering wave impacts and protecting shoreline. Oyster reefs have been shown to significantly reduce wave height, which is an indicator of wave energy (Wiberg et al., 2019). This reduction of waves by a structure is often referred to as wave attenuation. Wave attenuation is important for managing erosion and damage to shoreline. Degradation of oyster reef habitat has led to loss of shoreline protection ecosystem services, impacting coastal property values, cultural and social values, and tourism globally (Xu et al., 2024).

The effectiveness of oyster reef restoration projects is dependent on different reef characteristics like depth, reef shape and type (Wiberg et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2024). Artificial reefs can dissipate wave energy through friction with reef structure, reflection of wave energy, and wave breaking across the shallow reef. Restored reefs can expand in height, area, and roughness over time, which adapt the reef to rising sea levels and maintain the structure over time. This sustainable, nature-based solution offers coastal and marsh protection, while improving water quality and supporting habitat for marine life.

6.1.1 Methodology

To assess wave attenuation, we built custom wave pressure gauges ([Guidance Webb Lab](#)). The workflow to produce these gauges included programming, construction, deployment, and post-processing procedures. Components for each wave gauge included a pressure sensor, an arduino featherboard, battery, and silica packet, all enclosed in an airtight PVC pipe. The pressure sensors were sealed onto the PVC pipe on one end using cement glue and covered with a PVC cap with holes drilled into it to protect the sensor (Figure 6.1). The bottom end of the pipe is closed with a water tight gasket before deployment (Temple et al., 2020; Virden et al., 2023).

Figure 6.1: Wave gauge components.

Programming Wave Gauges

Our wave gauges were programmed using an Arduino featherboard. Each featherboard must have its own coin cell battery and microSD prior to programming and deployment. Using code produced by the Webb Lab, we tested the RTC (internal clock) and programmed for deployment using the delayed start and burst sampling scripts. There are a number of sampling styles available on his GitHub, including continuous and delayed sampling methods. We programmed our gauges to start sampling at the same time the next afternoon after deployment and take 15 minutes of burst observations every 15 minutes to save battery life (Figure 6.2).

Figure 6.2: Wave gauge deployment in the field.

Deployment

Our wave gauges were fixed to concrete blocks connected to buoys for visibility during high tide. We deployed the gauges behind and adjacent to each oyster reef at each site. We tried to select similar elevations and fetch for deployed wave gauge to be able to estimate the protection from the restored oyster reef on the shoreline. Gauges were placed parallel to the adjacent shoreline. More detailed methodology can be found in Appendix E - Wave Gauge SOP.

6.1.2 Results

Figure 6.3: Tide-filtered wave power measured behind and near the reef at each site.

Figure 6.4: Tide-filtered wave power time series (first day of datalogging after deployment) for each site. Breaks in time series are when the gauges were out of the water.

Figure 6.5: Tide-filtered wave power reduction for each site.

Due to issues with wave gauges discussed below, data comparing wave attenuation across reef types is limited; however, our study does show that multiple artificial and natural reef sites in the region provide wave attenuation services. Multiple sites showed a reduction in wave power behind the reef structure compared to adjacent reef area (Figure 6.3). When submerged, wave gauges revealed higher wave power in unprotected areas adjacent to reef modules versus protected areas shoreward of oyster reefs (Figure 6.4). When comparing limited data for natural and artificial reef types, both reef types were found to reduce wave power. Reduction of wave power across reef sites ranged from over 5% to an over 25% reduction depending on site (Figure 6.5). Overall, natural and artificial reef sites were shown to provide wave attenuation services in the region.

DIY wave gauges can be a cost-effective method of quantifying wave attenuation. When data is logged and analyzed correctly, it can provide valuable insight on how well restored reefs are meeting desired functions of wave attenuation and shoreline protection. However, there are a number of caveats to address when programming, deploying, and recovering wave gauges. Once wave gauges are deployed, you have little control over them in the field as factors like boat wake can interfere with data collection. Datasets can return broken or missing altogether, so this method should be coupled with other assessments. Multiple deployments and prolonged data collection can help you build a more robust dataset and contribute to a comprehensive assessment of oyster reef health and function.

While wave gauges can be a powerful and useful tool for quantifying wave attenuation, it is important to note that they require sufficient time, effort, funding, and expertise to be effective. Pre-assembled wave gauges are expensive, and DIY can be a viable option if executed correctly. However, between the assembly, coding, deployment, and recovery, there are many variables that can result in inconsistent data collection. We ran into a number of challenges during our assessment with the wave gauges, including gauges falling off of their cement blocks, flooded batteries and boards, inconsistent timestamps, and sites collecting more data than others. It's important to consider these limitations while following the SOPs, as some problems can be addressed in the instructions and many fixes can only be done before deployment. A comprehensive assessment of reef establishment and development, including sediment characteristics, oyster recruitment, and water quality is more critical to monitoring reef conditions than wave gauges could provide alone. Since collecting wave attenuation data is challenging and resource intensive, we only recommend utilizing wave gauges if shoreline protection was an explicit project goal and practitioners possess a background utilizing similar technologies.

6.2 Sediment Characteristics

In addition to wave attenuation, restored oyster reefs reduce erosion of the shoreline, protecting housing, infrastructure, and natural upland habitat. Vertical growth of oyster reefs can provide longer-term shore stabilization and protection as sea levels rise. This stabilization also contributes to sediment accumulation as waves are slowed by the reef, decreasing their erosive power. Trapped sediment builds upon the existing shoreline and can lead to the expansion of salt marsh or seagrass beds. This cascading effect results in habitat formation and enhances ecosystem services. Studies have shown that sites with oyster reefs experience less shoreline retreat compared to shorelines without reefs, facilitating seaward expansion of salt marshes (Chowdhury et al., 2019; Morris et al., 2019).

6.2.1 Methodology

Sediment accumulation

For this investigation, we used a sediment core made of a plexiglass tube, water tight gasket, PVC, and wood pole, to place a sediment plate behind the reef and adjacent to the reef at each site (Figure 6.6). We tried to place these plates at similar elevations to account for tidal regimes. To measure sediment accretion, we placed a vinyl circular plate under >5cm of soil that we were able to lift with the sediment corer (Ewers Lewis & McGlathery, 2023). To mark the location of the sediment plate, we stuck four PVC rods around the burial location. After the plate was buried, we used a thin steel rod and a yardstick to measure the depth of the plate in 3 random

locations on the plate surface and calculated the average depth of the plate at deployment. We revisited the site monthly over the summer, measuring the depth of the sediment plate using the same rod and method used during deployment to evaluate sediment deposition or erosion behind/near the restored reef.

Figure 6.6: Components of sediment corer.

Sediment composition

To evaluate sediment composition behind and adjacent to the reef, we used our sediment corer to take samples at >5cm deep, labeling and storing them in plastic bags. We kept the samples refrigerated until we could process them. At the lab, we put the samples into aluminum trays and placed them in a drying oven at 60C for several days to dry the sample. Once the samples were dry, we used a mortar and pestle to grind the samples until sandy and disaggregated. To measure percent organic matter through loss on ignition, we took sub samples of about 10g and placed them into aluminum dishes. The samples were then placed in a muffle furnace at 500C for 12-15 hours to burn off organic matter content. Samples were weighed again after burning to calculate percent organic matter lost in the furnace (Heiri et al., 2001). To measure particle size, we took the larger dried samples and sieved in a 7-level sieve, shaking for 10 minutes and weighing each mesh and the pan. The mesh and pan weights were subtracted to

get sediment weights at each level. More detailed methodology can be found in Appendix F - Sediment Characteristics SOP.

6.2.2 Results

Sediment characteristics reveal variability across restored and natural sites. Oyster reefs can absorb wave energy and support soil conditions for the accumulation of organic matter, since lower energy areas (created by an oyster reef wavebreak) can facilitate the build up of fine grain sediments. In our comparison of artificial and natural reefs in the southern IRL and SLE, sediment samples near natural reefs were found to contain a higher percentage of organic matter than samples near artificial reefs (Figure 6.9). Our results showed that despite the advanced age of the artificial reefs in this study, sediment characteristics still differed between artificial and natural reef sites. Despite observing wave reduction across reef types, sediment characteristics differed in several key metrics. Distribution of sediment grain size classes differed between natural and artificial reefs (Figure 6.7). Median grain size was also found to be higher for artificial reef sites compared to natural reef sites (Figure 6.8). Our results suggest that deployment of artificial reefs may not drastically change site sediment characteristics within a 6-14 year timescale post-restoration in the southern IRL and SLE.

Figure 6.7: Distribution of Grain Sizes for natural and restored sites.

Figure 6.8: Median Grain Size (D50) by site type

Figure 6.9: Organic Matter Percentage at natural vs. restored sites.

While collecting sediment characteristic data is sometimes feasible, we do not recommend measuring sediment characteristics as part of a long-term reef monitoring assessment. Processing sediment samples requires specialized laboratory equipment (muffle furnace), and according to our data sediment characteristics of artificial reefs do not match natural reefs after an extended period of time (6-14 years post-deployment). However, collecting sediment accumulation and characteristic data in conjunction with wave gauge data is helpful to better understand shoreline protection services as a whole. Therefore, we recommend practitioners utilize sediment accumulation and characteristic methodology if specifically interested in measuring shoreline protection ecosystem services and have the required resources and expertise.

7.0 Habitat Provisioning

Oyster reefs provide habitat for a host of organisms, including small fish and motile macroinvertebrates. Many species feed directly on live oysters, use shells as refuge from predation, or use habitat for spawning and reproduction. Oyster reefs establish an essential baseline for complex food webs, filtering nutrients from the surrounding water column and converting energy into a complex living reef structure (Tolley & Volety, 2005). Oyster reefs facilitate biodiversity by providing structure as well as refuge from abiotic and biotic stressors for other organisms (Reeves et al., 2020). Oyster reefs in the southeastern U.S. have a tangible impact on fish and large mobile crustacean abundance, with a 10m² functioning oyster reef projected to produce 2.6kg of production of fish and large mobile crabs per year (Peterson et al., 2003).

Species richness, species abundance, and species diversity are all useful metrics to quantify habitat provisioning ecosystem services. Species richness is the number of unique species in an area. High species richness lends itself to more resilient and sustainable ecosystems. Species abundance is the number of individuals of a particular species. Measuring abundance of oyster-associated species can gauge the habitat provisioning impact of reef habitat. Sampling for species abundance of oyster predators can also provide insight on reef health and persistence. Species richness and species abundance are typically considered together to better understand species diversity, the number of species and their relative abundance. Species diversity is an important parameter studied in all ecosystems, used to better understand community ecology.

While habitat provisioning is an important ecosystem service of oyster reef habitat, habitat provisioning metrics (species richness, species abundance, and species diversity) may not be reliable indicators of oyster reef health and success. Multiple studies show habitat provisioning metrics of restored reefs trending towards metrics of natural reefs within the first few years as abundance of live oyster increases (Hemraj et al., 2022; Jud & Layman, 2020; Karp et al., 2018; Searles et al., 2022; Smith et al., 2022). While other studies show that shell-cultch habitat and healthy oyster habitat produce similar measures of species abundance, species richness, and species diversity despite shell-cultch habitat lacking live oyster (Boudreaux et al., 2006; Tolley & Volety, 2005). Therefore, the structure provided by oyster shell-cultch may be an important mechanism for providing habitat in addition to the services provided by live oyster, and habitat provisioning metrics may not be reliable measures of oyster reef health and artificial oyster reef success. However, habitat provisioning is an important ecosystem service of reef habitat and should be quantified for restoration projects in which habitat provisioning is an explicit goal, and can be quantified for all reefs to understand community ecology.

7.1.1 Methodology

Habitat provisioning services were quantified using habitat trays, identifying and enumerating captured motile macroinvertebrates and small fishes. Species-level identification of estuarine macroinvertebrates requires microscope analysis of culled specimens and identification training, which is typically beyond the scope of most practitioners. Therefore, during this study captured organisms were usually classified into families and superfamilies, as live specimens can typically be categorized into these groups based on morphology and released back into the habitat. More detailed information regarding these methodologies can be found in the Habitat Provisioning SOP, Appendix G.

Three habitat trays were deployed at each reef site for a two month deployment time (L. Baggett, 2014; Janiak et al., 2021). Habitat trays were constructed of plastic dishwashing machine crates (50cm x 25cm) lined with aquaculture mesh (0.06mm openings) and buried into the reef surface so that only the top of the tray was exposed (Figure 7.1). The tray was then filled with displaced reef material, so that contents of the tray mimicked the surrounding reef material composition and density (Janiak et al., 2021). Tray locations were spread across the site, prioritizing areas with greatest live oyster cover. After the two-month deployment, trays were collected at negative low tide. Tray contents were sorted and all motile invertebrates and small fishes with adult sizes over 5mm were collected, placed into 5-gallon buckets with clean oyster shell-culch, and brought back to the lab for processing. All reef material was returned to the tray location immediately upon sorting to minimize impact to reef structure. Sensitive organisms (e.g. fishes) were identified and enumerated in the field and immediately returned to the reef. Live motile macroinvertebrates were identified to the lowest possible taxonomic group (typically families and superfamilies), enumerated, and photographed at the lab. Organisms were returned to the appropriate reef sites within 48 hours according to the FWC special activities license.

Figure 7.1: Habitat tray deployed at an artificial reef site.

7.1.2 Results

Table 7.1: Total number of organisms sampled per taxonomic group by reef type.

Taxonomic group	Common Name	Total	Artificial reef	Natural reef
<i>Panopeidae</i>	Mud crab	1272	836	436
<i>Petrolisthes armatus</i>	Porcelain crab	872	519	353
<i>Alpheidae</i>	Snapping shrimp	86	84	2
<i>Grapsoidae</i>	Shore crab	40	24	16
<i>Muricidae</i>	Rock snail	35	35	0
<i>Nerita</i> spp.	Nerite snail	34	34	0
<i>Phrontis vibex</i>	Bruised nassa snail	12	12	0
<i>Stylochus</i> spp.	Oyster flatworm	12	12	0
<i>Polychaeta</i>	Bristleworm	11	9	2
<i>Clibanarius vittatus</i>	Striped hermit crab	9	9	0

Taxonomic group	Common Name	Total	Artificial reef	Natural reef
<i>Gobiidae</i>	Goby	9	9	0
<i>Sipuncula</i>	Peanut worm	7	7	0
Unidentified gastropod A	N/A	6	6	0
<i>Cerithioidea</i>	Cerith snail	5	5	0
<i>Gobiesox strumosus</i>	Skilletfish	5	5	0
<i>Libinia</i> spp.	Decorator crab	4	4	0
<i>Menippe mercenaria</i>	Stone crab	3	3	0
Unidentified clam	N/A	2	0	2
Unidentified gastropod B	N/A	2	1	1
<i>Vitta</i> spp.	Nerite snail	2	1	1
<i>Calyptraeidae</i>	Slipper snail	1	1	0
<i>Ligia</i> spp.	Wharf roach	1	1	0
<i>Lucinidae</i>	Lucinid clam	1	1	0
<i>Mulinia lateralis</i>	Dwarf surf clam	1	1	0
<i>Myrophis punctatus</i>	Speckled worm eel	1	0	1

Artificial reefs exceeded natural reefs in all habitat provisioning metrics for motile macroinvertebrates and small resident fishes. Our analysis is unable to provide insight regarding species richness, as organisms were typically classified to the superfamily or family taxonomic level (Table 7.1). Sampling revealed 23 distinct taxonomic groups utilizing artificial reefs and 9 groups utilizing natural reefs, with 7 groups present on both reef types. Artificial reefs displayed a greater number of taxonomic groups compared to natural reefs. Much of the diversity is lost by grouping organisms into higher taxonomic groups; therefore, our results underrepresent actual species diversity. For example, the family *Panopeidae* (mud crabs) contains approximately 11 species in the IRL region, but was grouped together for analysis as species identification is difficult and requires advanced training and culling of organisms.

In addition to higher richness of taxonomic groups, artificial reefs also showed higher abundances of organisms than natural reefs. Decapods (crabs and shrimps) and gastropods (snails) were some of the most frequently occurring organisms, with artificial reefs having the same or greater abundances of every taxonomic group identified within those broad categories (Figures 7.2 and 7.3). The only taxonomic groups that did not have higher abundances on artificial reefs were *Myrophis punctatus* (speckled worm eel) (natural = 1, artificial = 0), *Vitta* spp. (nerite snail) (natural = 1, artificial = 1), unidentified gastropod B (natural = 1, artificial = 1), and unidentified clam (natural = 2, artificial = 1). All other taxonomic groups had higher abundances on artificial reefs, including common resident mud crabs (*Panopeidae*) with abundances on artificial reefs reaching almost double that of natural reefs (artificial = 836, natural = 436). When comparing medians of the two most common taxonomic groups (*Panopeidae* and *Petrolisthes armatus*), this stark pattern remains. The median number of total *Panopeidae* found on artificial reefs was 40.5 versus 18.5 for natural reefs. *Petrolisthes armatus* is a non-native but abundant species of crab commonly found on oyster reef habitats. Median number of *Petrolisthes armatus* found on artificial reefs is 13.5 versus 5.5 for natural reefs. Abundances of other common oyster reef residents such as *Alphidae* (snapping shrimp), *Grapsoidae* (shore crab), and *Muricidae* (rock snail) were clearly higher on artificial reefs than natural reefs.

Figure 7.2: Decapod (crab and shrimp) taxonomic group abundance by reef type.

Figure 7.3: Gastropod (snail) taxonomic group abundance by reef type.

Considering richness and abundance together, artificial reefs show higher diversity than natural reefs. Artificial reefs exceeding natural reefs in richness, abundance, and diversity is unexpected, as most literature shows restored reefs as underperforming or similar to natural reefs in habitat provisioning metrics. To explore potential drivers in differences between sites, we visualized the relationship between density of live oyster and abundance of *Panopeidae* and *Menippidae* crabs, as well as percent cover of live oyster and abundance of *Panopeidae* and *Menippidae* crabs. *Panopeidae* (mud crab) and *Menippidae* (stone crab) crabs are common oyster reef residents with similar morphology, and their abundances have been used to evaluate success of reef restoration projects in Chesapeake Bay (Smith et al., 2022). In this study, scatterplot visualization showed a weak potential positive relationship between oyster density and crab abundance and no potential relationship between percent cover of live oyster and mud crab abundance (Figures 7.4 and 7.5).

Figure 7.4: Average mud and stone crab abundance in relationship to average oyster density per square meter by site.

Figure 7.5: Average mud and stone crab abundance in relationship to average percent cover of live oyster per square meter by site.

Our analysis suggests that in the southern IRL and SLE, habitat provisioning services of oyster reefs may not be primarily driven by oyster density but rather physical structure of shell-cultch. Artificial reefs in our study are composed of shell-cultch in plastic mesh bags that are stacked into modules and placed on top of the sediment. This bagged oyster cultch structure can provide extensive interstitial space and habitat for a variety of organisms, regardless of live oyster abundance.

Based on our data, habitat provisioning metrics do not reflect overall reef restoration success metrics. When conducting long-term monitoring of mature artificial oyster reef projects, quantifying reef development and persistence data should be paramount. Since habitat provisioning metrics do not correlate with priority reef health metrics and collecting habitat provisioning data is time and resource intensive, we only recommend collecting habitat tray data if specifically interested in that particular ecosystem service or if habitat provisioning was an explicit project goal.

8.0 Water Quality

The oyster lifecycle consists of multiple phases that are affected by salinity and temperature (Gregory et al., 2023; Wallace et al., 2008). Salinity and temperature are master factors in aquatic environments, determining the habitat ranges of organisms. As sessile organisms, salinity and temperature determine oyster reef health and persistence.

Salinity affects adult oyster gametogenesis, disease intensification, and larval growth and development (Chu, 1996; Dekshenieks et al., 1993; Gregory et al., 2023; Heilmayer et al., 2008). Adult eastern oysters are found in habitats with salinities ranging from 5-40ppt (Heilmayer et al., 2008). If salinities drop below 5ppt, oysters experience depressed gametogenesis and larval growth ceases. Salinities between 17.5-25ppt demonstrate higher larval growth rates; however, prevalence and intensity of dermo disease increases with higher salinities. Today, extensive oyster reefs are not found in the main portion of the southern IRL where salinities are high and stable (Radabaugh et al., 2019). Instead, the largest reef structures are found within tributaries (i.e. SLE) where salinities are lower and fluctuating (Radabaugh et al., 2019). Salinity also greatly affects community assemblages of oyster reefs with higher salinity reefs typically showing increased species richness and prevalence of oyster predators.

Water temperature determines oyster growth and development, as well as disease prevalence and intensity (Chu, 1996; Dekshenieks et al., 1993; Okon et al., 2023; Shumway, 1996). Adult eastern oysters can survive in water temperatures from -2C-36C, with ideal temperatures occurring from 20-30C. Warmer water temperatures promote longer spawning seasons and increased oyster growth rates; however, high temperatures (over 30C) increase physiological stress, disease prevalence, and disease intensity.

Salinity and temperature have synergistic effects on oyster life stages, oyster health, reef development, reef persistence, and reef community assemblage (Chu, 1996; Coxe et al., 2023; Heilmayer et al., 2008; McFarland et al., 2022). For example, salinity extremes can become lethal in summer months due to a combination of temperature and salinity stress (McFarland et al., 2022). Meanwhile, oysters can deal with temperature stress if salinities are within optimal range and vice versa (Heilmayer et al., 2008).

Understanding effects of abiotic factors can help better plan oyster restoration projects and interpret monitoring data (L. P. Baggett et al., 2015; Beck et al., 2011; Parker & Radigan, 2020). Salinity and temperature are considered universal environmental variables that should be monitored according to the Oyster Habitat Restoration Monitoring and Assessment Handbook to better understand causes of project success/failure (L. Baggett, 2014). Dissolved oxygen is considered a universal environmental variable for subtidal reefs; however, since this project focuses on intertidal reefs, dissolved oxygen was not monitored.

8.1.1 Methodology

Temperature and salinity data can be acquired in a variety of ways including regional publicly available water quality data, YSI grab samples, and data loggers. Publicly available water quality data in the region includes South Florida Water Management District (SFWMD) DBHydro, Indian River Lagoon Observatory Network (IRLON), and Ocean Research and Conservation Association (ORCA) Kilroy Network. Analyzing temperature and salinity measures from nearby water quality monitoring stations can provide valuable insight for interpretation of data, revealing longer term water quality conditions that affect reef health and persistence. Meanwhile, YSI grab samples can be helpful to understand water conditions at a particular time and location. YSI grab samples can be compared to data from water quality monitoring stations to better utilize continuous public data and understand site specific differences. For this research, we utilized HOBO Conductivity Loggers to best understand temperature and salinity regimes of each reef site.

Nine HOBO Conductivity Loggers (conductivity and temperature) were deployed across 12 reef sites, with one data logger deployed for two sites when sites were in close proximity (Figure 8.1). Conductivity loggers were deployed adjacent to reefs in the subtidal zone by attaching loggers to PVC poles with zip ties (Figure 8.2). Loggers were placed to maximize submergence time and data collection, with loggers wrapped in electrical tape and panty hose to prevent fouling. Specific conductivity and water temperature measurements were collected every hour. During monthly data offloads, loggers were defouled and in-situ YSI measurements were taken to calibrate logger measurements. For more information and detailed methodology, please refer to Appendix H - Water Quality (HOBO U-24 Logger) SOP.

Figure 8.1: Map of general salinity logger locations labeled by site name. Loggers were placed offshore of reef sites. Green points signify natural reef locations, purple points signify artificial reef locations in the IRL, and blue points signify artificial reef locations in the SLE.

Figure 8.2: Researcher deploying HOBOLogger by attaching to PVC with zipties.

8.1.2 Results

Salinity

Figure 8.3: Salinity measured by dataloggers over summer 2025 in the southern IRL and SLE. Warm colors denote dataloggers deployed in the IRL and cool colors denote dataloggers deployed in the SLE.

Salinity data reflected expected summer trends for the southern IRL and SLE. Southern IRL sites experienced consistently high salinities, with an average salinity of 30.05 ppt for sites in the IRL (Figure 8.3). Minimum salinity detected across IRL sites was 3.36 ppt; however, this was likely a small localized event or logger error as salinities at most sites did not drop below 20 ppt over the duration of the study. Maximum salinity detected in the IRL was 39.67 ppt. Sites in the SLE experienced lower salinities and were more varied, with an average salinity of 13.05 ppt, a minimum of 1.30 ppt, and a maximum of 25.29 ppt across sites (Table 8.1). A salinity gradient was easily identifiable for SLE sites, with salinity decreasing upriver and increasing with proximity to the IRL. These results are expected, as reefs in the IRL basin receive oceanic water from the St Lucie and Fort Pierce Inlets, while reefs in the SLE receive a combination of freshwater from the St Lucie River and saline water from the IRL. The salinity data shows that oyster reefs up river have lower salinities than reefs downstream, and that reefs in the IRL experience consistently high salinities.

Table 8.1: Salinity measurements by site across summer months in the southern IRL and SLE.

Logger Site	Waterbody	Mean SAL (ppt)	Min SAL (ppt)	Max SAL (ppt)
JACK	IRL	32.85	18.93	36.73
WC	IRL	32.04	24.35	39.67
BERG	IRL	29.50	3.36	34.90
DW	IRL	28.12	21.15	35.92
IRSP*	IRL*	26.08*	21.68*	30.48*
ES*	SLE*	17.57*	7.54*	25.29*
ROSE*	SLE*	12.34*	2.92*	24.77*
FL*	SLE*	10.70*	4.05*	19.14*
PEN	SLE	12.31	1.30	21.29

*Only includes data from end of June to beginning of September (no data from end of April to mid-June)

Temperature

Figure 8.4: Temperatures recorded by dataloggers over summer 2025 in the southern IRL and SLE.

Temperature data was similar between sites and waterbodies. The average temperature for IRL sites was 30.39C, with a minimum temperature of 22.29C and maximum temperature of 38.26C across sites. In the SLE the average temperature was found to be 31.44C, with a minimum temperature of 24.86C and a maximum temperature of 40.09C (Figure 8.4; Table 8.2). As expected, oyster reefs in the southern IRL and SLE are experiencing high temperatures across the summer months, with temperatures climbing throughout the summer. The highest temperature (40.09) was logged at the datalogger site PEN (near PENN and PEND reef sites), the farthest upstream site in the SLE near the end of July.

Logger Site	Waterbody	Mean temp (C)	Min temp (C)	Max temp (C)
JACK	IRL	29.21	24.07	34.54
WC	IRL	30.60	24.22	35.79
BERG	IRL	30.63	22.29	38.26
DW	IRL	30.71	23.44	37.50
IRSP*	IRL*	31.10*	27.18*	37.30*
ES*	SLE*	31.43*	27.86*	36.12*
ROSE*	SLE*	30.87*	27.90*	33.97*
FL*	SLE*	31.90*	28.46*	37.99*
PEN	SLE	31.52	24.86	40.09

Table 8.2: Temperature measurements by site across summer months in the southern IRL and SLE.

*Only includes data from end of June to beginning of September (no data from end of April to mid-June)

Salinity and temperature have synergistic effects on oyster reef health and persistence (Heilmayer et al., 2008; McFarland et al., 2022). Our data reinforces the knowledge that oyster reefs in the IRL experience consistently high temperatures and salinities throughout the summer months, which can increase disease susceptibility and advancement (Chu, 1996). Meanwhile, oysters in the SLE can experience a deadly combination of extreme low salinities and high temperatures (Heilmayer et al., 2008). Laboratory experiments have shown that temperatures over 30C, such as the temperatures detected by dataloggers throughout the summer in the southern IRL and SLE, can amplify negative effects of salinity extremes (McFarland et al., 2022). The temperatures recorded on the dataloggers are likely conservative values, since dataloggers had to be placed in deeper waters offshore of most reefs in order to stay submerged

during negative low tides. It is likely that actual shallow water temperature values on the reef surface are higher.

Salinity and temperature are considered universal environmental variables that should be monitored according to the Oyster Habitat Restoration Monitoring and Assessment Handbook (L. Baggett, 2014). Understanding temperature and salinity regimes of a site is extremely important for site selection and to understand potential drivers of reef success or failure; however, continuous water quality monitoring with dataloggers is not always feasible for a long-term post-restoration reef quick assessment. In our study, utilizing HOBologgers was helpful to understand site specific dynamics; however, dataloggers are expensive and servicing loggers can be resource intensive. Thankfully, water quality data for the southern IRL and SLE is publicly available and can be easily utilized by practitioners.

9.0 Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on findings from our study in the southern IRL and SLE, we strongly recommend oyster reef restoration practitioners implement long-term monitoring for artificial reefs to capture development of ecosystem services in the region (Table 9.1).

At a minimum, practitioners should sample for substrate composition (percent cover), density of live oyster, and size class frequency to determine reef development of artificial reef sites over the long term. Without these three basic metrics, long-term effectiveness of oyster reef restoration projects cannot be quantified. Percent cover serves as a simple, practical, and effective visual indicator of reef health and progression, with visibility of plastic as an added simple visual assessment of development. Density of live oyster and size class frequency distribution are essential metrics to understand oyster population structure and health. Typically density and size class frequency data is collected via excavations; however, our study was able to implement non-destructive methods to collect this vital data.

When conducting long-term monitoring, we also strongly suggest collecting data for reef area, reef height, and reef rugosity as well as incorporating water quality data to best understand reef health, development, and persistence. Collecting reef persistence data using methods described in this quick assessment guide is cost-effective, simple, and easy to incorporate into a monitoring protocol along with reef development metrics. Reef area is an important metric for calculating reef size, extrapolating reef density and composition metrics, and estimating impacts of ecosystem services (L. Baggett, 2014). Reef height is an important determining factor in restored reef persistence, especially when practitioners are able to compare data to original deployment height and/or nearby natural reef heights. Collection of reef rugosity data is simple and cost-effective, providing helpful additional data to characterize reef sites. In addition to reef persistence metrics, we also strongly suggest incorporating water quality data (temperature and salinity) to ensure practitioners understand basic abiotic factors that could be driving patterns discerned through reef development, persistence, and health sampling. While deploying dataloggers is not often feasible, we encourage practitioners to explore the continuous water quality data provided by multiple agencies and institutions in the region.

Additional reef development and health metrics can be included in long-term monitoring plans if questions arise regarding driving factors of restoration success/failure after implementing the long-term monitoring strategies listed above. Collecting Condition Index data can be helpful to better understand the health of oyster populations. We recommend practitioners interested in oyster health utilize the condition index scale described by Quick & Mackin (1971) as a relatively simple way to assess oyster health without access to an institutional laboratory. If practitioners have access to a laboratory and their study reef sites exist in high salinity environments, we recommend collecting data to quantify prevalence and density of Dermo disease as described in this guide. Understanding spat settlement is vital for pre-restoration monitoring; however, based on our study, we conclude that size class frequency metrics should

be prioritized over spat recruitment methodology in long-term post-restoration monitoring. Due to the time intensive nature of spat monitoring, we would recommend implementing oyster settlement monitoring when reef development metrics show low densities and percent cover of live oyster, and size class frequency data shows low frequencies of recruit size oysters. If artificial reefs sites do not seem to be coalescing (seem to have high percent coverage of original restoration materials) and the reef site experiences high salinities, we recommend collecting data to examine oyster species composition to understand the proportion of different bivalve species such as crested oysters and flat tree oysters. Collection of oyster species composition data is very cost-effective, and can easily be worked into an existing monitoring protocol.

To evaluate the development of ecosystem services, additional protocols can be incorporated into a long-term monitoring plan to evaluate success of specific project goals. Collecting habitat provisioning data with habitat trays is a cost-effective and practical way to acquire richness, abundance, and diversity data of groups of motile macroinvertebrates and small resident fish. Species-level identification of estuarine macroinvertebrates is typically beyond the scope of most practitioners; however, categorizing organisms into higher level taxonomic groups still revealed patterns of community structure. In this study, we found that richness, abundances, and diversity of taxonomic groups did not reflect patterns of reef development. We also found habitat tray sampling to be very time intensive. Therefore, we recommend implementing habitat tray monitoring if habitat provisioning was an original project goal or a particular subject of interest, but not as a necessary long-term reef monitoring technique.

While wave gauges can be a powerful and useful tool for quantifying wave attenuation, it is important to note that they require sufficient time, effort, funding, and expertise to be effective. Pre-assembled wave gauges are expensive, and DIY can be a viable option if executed correctly. However, between the assembly, coding, deployment, and recovery, there are many variables that can result in inconsistent data collection. Therefore, we recommend implementing DIY wave gauge monitoring if practitioners have necessary resources. Sediment characteristics data provides helpful context for wave gauge data. Collecting sediment accretion measurements via sediment plates can be difficult in sediments with high abundance of shells, and analysis of sediment composition data as described in this guidance document requires access to an institutional lab with a muffle furnace. We recommend implementing wave gauge and sediment characteristic monitoring as described in this guide in situations when practitioners are not limited by time and resource constraints, as these methodologies are not suitable for a rapid reef assessment.

Table 9.1: Recommendations for long term reef monitoring based on constraints

Monitoring Suggestions	Approaches	Constraints and Needs	Relevant SOP
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<i>Bare Minimum Monitoring</i>	Substrate Composition (Percent Cover)	Site access, minimal supplies, staff time	Appendix B - Reef Monitoring
	Density of live oyster	Site access, minimal supplies, staff time	Appendix B - Reef Monitoring
	Size class frequencies	Site access, minimal supplies, staff time	Appendix B - Reef Monitoring
<i>Practical Monitoring</i>	Reef area	Site access, minimal supplies, staff time	Appendix B - Reef Monitoring
	Reef height	Site access, minimal supplies, staff time	Appendix B - Reef Monitoring
	Reef Rugosity	Site access, minimal supplies, staff time	Appendix B - Reef Monitoring
	Water Temperature and Salinity	Site access, access to loggers, staff time	Appendix H - Water Quality
	Condition Index	Site access, permit to collect oysters, staff time	Appendix C - Condition Index
<i>Intensive Monitoring</i>	Presence of Dermo Disease	Site access, permit to collect oysters, laboratory access, staff time	Appendix D - Perkinsus Marinus (Dermo)
	Spat Recruitment	Site access, permitting for oyster Ts, minimal supplies, Monthly staff time	Appendix A - Spat Recruitment
	Habitat Provisioning	Site access, minimal supplies, permit for collection, staff time for collection and processing	Appendix G - Habitat Trays Appendix I - Invertebrate Identification Appendix J - Fish Identification
	Wave Attenuation	Site access, more extensive supplies, time to learn how to	Appendix E - Wave Gauges

		put together wave gauges, program them and process them, repeat visits to the site for data collection	
	Sediment Plates and Characteristics	Site access, minimal supplies, repeat visits to a site for data collection, access to laboratory	Appendix F - Sediment Characteristics

10.0 Appendices

Appendix A- Spat Recruitment SOP

Spat Monitoring Standard Operating Procedure

Original procedure written by Phillips, Z., Zugelster, A., Cole, S., & Simpson, L., Florida Oceanographic Society

Updated and edited by Emily Surmont, University of Florida, FDEP Indian River Lagoon Aquatic Preserves

EQUIPMENT CHECKLIST

Oyster T and Oyster Stringer Construction

- Cordless drill
- Drill press
- Sharpie
- Measuring tape
- PVC pipe cutters
- 1/4" drill bit
- 1" PVC pipe
- 1" PVC tee fitting
- PVC cement
- 14 gauge galvanized wire
- Clean oyster shells
- Wire cutters
- Needle-nose pliers
- 5-gallon bucket

Initial field deployment

- Oyster Ts
- Rubber mallet
- Meter stick or stadia rod
- String
- Level
- Field notebook
- Pencils
- Oyster stringers (6 per site, plus extras)

Monthly monitoring

- Field notebook
- Pencils
- Oyster stringers (6 per site, plus extras)
- 5-gallon buckets

-
- Numbered tags
 - Tip: bring rubber mallet, extra oyster Ts, and a meter stick/stadia rod incase any oyster Ts are missing.

Oyster spat processing

- Datasheets
- Observation trays labeled #1-7
- Dissection lamp
- Probing tool set
- Wire cutters
- Ruler
- Camera
- 5-gallon buckets

OYSTER T AND OYSTER STRINGER CONSTRUCTION

Oyster T Construction (Figure A.1)

1. Using the measuring tape and sharpie, measure and mark the 1" PVC pipe into 3 separate sections, the first section measuring 3' in length, followed by 2 sections, both measuring 10" in length.
2. Use PVC pipe cutters to cut the PVC pipe along the measured lines.
3. Securely mount the two 10" sections of 1" PVC pipe to be drilled.
4. Using a cordless drill and 1/4" drill bit, drill a hole through one end of each 10" section of PVC pipe, approximately 1" from the end.
5. Using PVC cement, coat the inside of the centered opening of the 1" PVC tee fitting as well as the one exterior end of the 3' section of PVC pipe.
6. Then press the cemented PVC tee fitting onto the cemented end of the 3' PVC pipe and hold firmly for 30 seconds to prevent the connection from moving while it bonds.
7. Repeat the previous 2 steps, but with the non-drilled ends of the 10" PVC sections to the remaining openings on the PVC tee fitting (note: ensure the direction of the drilled holes run parallel to the 3' section of PVC pipe).
8. 3 oyster Ts should be deployed per site (n=3).

Figure A.1: Constructed oyster T (image credit: Florida Oceanographic Society).

Oyster Stringer Construction (Figure A.2)

1. Drill oyster shells
 - Oyster shells should be of a medium size ~ 3 inches long.
 - Using a drill press and 1/4" drill bit, position and secure an oyster shell with the interior/concave side facing up to prevent splitting and slowly drill a centered hole in the oyster shell.
 - Repeat the previous steps for the rest of the oyster shells.
2. Using wire cutters, cut a 20" (45 mm) section of 14ga wire.
3. Curl one end of the wire section with pliers for the bottom to be a stopper for shell (figure 3).
4. Thread the straight end of wire section through the hole drilled in oyster shell with the interior side of all oyster shells facing the curled end of the wire.
5. Mount exactly 7 oyster shells per wire.
6. By hand, curl the center of the wire above the mounted oyster shells to prevent shells from falling off when transporting.
7. Repeat the previous 3 steps for the remainder of the oyster stringers (note: 6 oyster stringers will be needed per site for 3 oyster Ts per site).

Figure A.2: Constructed oyster stringer (image credit: Florida Oceanographic Society)

INITIAL FIELD DEPLOYMENT

1. Aim to schedule field deployment with low tides, as this field work is very difficult at high tides.
 - NOAA Tide Predictions: https://tidesandcurrents.noaa.gov/tide_predictions.html
2. Using the meter stick/stadia rod, string, and level, take a rough reef height measurement (described in Oyster Reef Monitoring Procedure, Quick Assessment Guide, Appendix B). Record this measurement in the field notebook, as this measurement will be used as a reference range to position the oyster stringers in the water column.
3. Find a location adjacent to the oyster reef with a sandy or silty bottom.
4. Using a plastic or rubber mallet, hammer the oyster T into the substrate hitting it directly on the center of the PVC T fitting until the T is firmly secured in the sediment.
5. Mount one stringer on each side of the oyster T by threading the wire through the bottom of the drilled hole on each end of the oyster T.
6. Use the meter stick/stadia rod to adjust the position of the oyster stringer to the reference height measurement recorded in the field. The goal is for the oyster stringers to reflect reef height and submergence time. Secure the stringer by wrapping the end of the wire around the PVC pipe.
7. Repeat the previous steps for the remaining 2 oyster Ts (note: 3 Ts per site for a total of 6 stringers)

MONTHLY MONITORING

-
1. Aim to schedule field deployment with low tides, as this field work is very difficult at high tides.
 - NOAA Tide Predictions: https://tidesandcurrents.noaa.gov/tide_predictions.html
 2. Collect oyster stringers
 - Take stringer off and attach numbered tag to wire. All stringers should be tagged.
 - Write site and tag number in notebook
 - Record if the stringer was missing or found on sediment.
 - Place all stringers from each site in 1 bucket (tip: label bucket with site name using duct tape).
 - Fill bucket with water so that oyster shells are submerged.
 3. Replace oyster stringers
 - Mount one stringer on each side of the oyster T by threading the wire through the bottom of the drilled hole on each end of the oyster T.
 - Use the meter stick/stadia rod to adjust the position of the stringers to the reference height measurement recorded in the field notebook. The goal is for the oyster stringers to reflect reef height and submergence time. Secure the stringer by wrapping the end of the wire around the PVC pipe.
 - Repeat the previous steps for the remaining 2 oyster Ts.

OYSTER SPAT PROCESSING

1. Tip: Before starting, write steps out on whiteboard or print out instructions to ensure no steps are skipped.
2. Print a datasheet for each site.
3. Label observation tray 1-7 with masking tape and line up oysters from stringer.
 - #1 = top shell, #7 = bottom shell.
 - Lay all shell interior side up.
4. Record stringer tag number on datasheet.
5. Take photo of interior side of shell #3 and include numbered tag and ruler in photo (Figure A.3).
6. Discard shell #1 & shell #7 into 5-gallon discard bucket.
7. Enumerate the number of spat on each oyster shell and record on the datasheet.
8. It is recommended to use a dissecting needle from the probing tools kit to remove each live spat to keep track of the total count.
9. Remove macroalgae to ensure there are not spat beneath.
10. Any other organisms present, or abnormalities should be described under the notes column on the datasheet.

Figure A.3: Photo of shell interior with numbered tag and ruler.

OYSTER SPAT IDENTIFICATION

Oyster Spat vs Slipper Snail

Slipper snails (also known as slipper shells) are gastropods that can be easily mistaken for oyster spat. There are 5 species that can be found in the IRL region: Eastern White Slipper Snail (*Crepidula atrasolea*), Common Atlantic Slipper Snail (*Crepidula fornicate*), Convex Slipper Snail (*Crepidula convexa*), Depressed Slipper Snail (*Crepidula depressa*), and Spiny Slipper Snail (*Crepidula aculeata*). Slipper snails are considered common and should be considered when enumerating spat.

- Oyster spat grow into the stringer shell. They typically do not have clean edges and instead fan out onto shell. Meanwhile, slipper snails are individual motile organisms and appear to have clean shell margins as they do not grow into oyster shells.
- Slipper snails are motile organisms and can be moved using pressure. If oyster spat is removed, the oyster spat dies, and a mark is left behind from the bottom valve. If slipper snails are moved, there is no raised or visual mark left behind. The underside of slipper snails have a visual shelf.
- Spat often have purple streaking burst pattern typically originating near umbo and continuing along visible shell.

Figure A.4: Slipper snail (circled in red) amongst other organisms on an adult oyster shell.

Figure A.5: Left: slipper snail dorsal view; Right: slipper snail ventral view.

Oyster Spat vs Barnacles

Barnacles (*Balanus* spp.) are common crustaceans that can be mistaken for oyster spat. There are several species that can be found in the IRL region. Barnacles are extremely common and will be encountered at most sites when enumerating oyster spat.

- Oyster spat are typically smooth to the touch, while barnacles come to a point and are typically sharper to the touch.
- Oyster spat grow along the oyster shell surface becoming oblong like a rolling hill; meanwhile, barnacles can be compared to small volcanoes.

Figure A.6: Barnacles on an adult oyster shell.

Additional identification resources:

<https://shellfish.ifas.ufl.edu/clambag/bio-sketch-blob-like-encrusting.php>

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Appendix B- Reef Monitoring SOP

Oyster Reef Monitoring Standard Operating Procedure

EQUIPMENT CHECKLIST

- Datasheets
 - Percent cover & rugosity
 - Density & size class frequency
 - Reef height
- Pencils
- Random sampling grid
- Generated random sampling numbers
- 1m² grid quadrats
- 0.25m² quadrats (0.5m x 0.5m)
- Metal chain (ceiling fan chain)
- Transect tape
- Calipers (measure in mm)
- Flags
- Line level
- String
- Stadia rod
- Handheld GPS (Trimble handheld GPS, RTK GPS, etc)
- Clipboards
- Gloves
- Permits/Special Activity License (SAL) (laminated)

PREPARATION

1. Special Activities License is required from the Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission to conduct the following monitoring procedure. Also, a verification of exemption should be acquired from the appropriate water management district for any sampling equipment being deployed in submerged lands.
2. Create random sampling grid & generate random numbers
 - Superimpose a numbered grid on an aerial photograph of the reef or create a simple map based on rough reef measurements. Reef length and width measurements were taken using transect tape and drawn onto gridded paper (Figure B.1).
 - Use the random number generator at [random.org/integers](https://www.random.org/integers), to produce random numbers for quadrat monitoring (Baggett et al., 2024).
 - Percent cover, density & size class frequency, and rugosity data can be collected at the same random locations.

3. Schedule reef monitoring for extreme low tides for accuracy and ease of data collection.
 - NOAA Tide Predictions: https://tidesandcurrents.noaa.gov/tide_predictions.html
 - In the southern IRL, reef monitoring was scheduled for tides lower than or equal to -0.05 at the Jensen Beach Causeway station and lower than or equal to -1.0 at the Binney Dock station.
 - In the SLE, reef monitoring was scheduled for tides lower than or equal to -0.10 at the Stuart station.

Figure B.1: Two simple random sampling grids created for summer 2025 monitoring.

FIELD PROCEDURE

1. Percent cover: quadrat sampling (based on Janiak, 2021)
 - Using a 1m² grid quadrat, count the substrate type that occurs under each cross string and tally in the appropriate category on the datasheet. Major categories include:
 - Live oyster
 - Gaper oyster (gaping dying oyster with visible tissue, uncommon)
 - Box oyster (gaping dead with both shells still attached, no visible tissue)
 - Cultch (dead with only single shell remaining)
 - Shell hash
 - Sediment
 - Algae (be specific if possible)
 - Rock
 - Any other groups (bivalves, ascidians, sponges, etc.) using lowest taxonomic classification as possible. Ensure to note if the point falls on a flat tree oyster (*Isognomon alatus*) (see oyster species composition below).
 - For artificial or restored reefs where restoration material (plastic, metal, concrete, etc) is found at the point-intercept, count the restoration material as well as the

reef substrate found beneath. Also note if the restoration material is covered in macroalgae or other organisms.

- o For example, if plastic bag material occurs over top of shell cultch at the point-intercept, place a “P” instead of a tally mark in the shell cultch category of the datasheet. If the same plastic is covered in algae, place “PA” in the shell cultch category.
- After counting, add all the tallies to ensure 81 points have been counted.

Live oyster	Boxed oyster	Cultch	Shell hash
<p data-bbox="1131 1003 1313 1037">Pieces of shell</p>			

Figure B.2: Examples of different substrate types observed in percent cover monitoring.

2. Rugosity: chain and tape (based on Janiak, 2021)

- At the same location where percent cover data was collected, lay 1m of transect tape straight across the reef surface. Keep the transect tape as straight and taut as possible. The transect tape can be laid to the side of the quadrat or within the quadrat area, to ensure the rugosity measurement reflects the composition of the quadrat area.
- Lay a chain alongside the transect tape, placing the chain to conform to the reef. When laying the chain, conform the chain to the substrate by slowly dropping the chain vertically working from one end to the other. Do not push the chain against overhanging portions of the substrate. Instead, lay the chain over the upper surface of the substrate and drop the chain down into lower portions of the substrate.
- Measure the distance that the chain reaches using the transect tape and record on the data sheet.

Figure B.3: (Left) Figure depicting rugosity measurement procedure from Janiak, 2021; (Right) Photo of researcher collecting rugosity data.

3. Density & size frequency: quadrat sampling (based on Baggett et al., 2014; Janiak, 2021; Cole, 2023)
 - Remove the 1m² grid quadrat previously used for percent cover sampling, and place a 0.25m² quadrat randomly within the 1m² area.
 - Measure the shell height of the first 50 live oysters found on the surface of the reef within the quadrat using calipers. Shell height should be measured from the umbo to the furthest extent of the shell. Only include oysters with shell heights greater than 10mm. To minimize damage to the reef, only oysters on the surface of the reef within the quadrat should be counted and measured.
 - After 50 live oysters have been measured, count the rest of the live oysters greater than or equal to 10mm on the surface of the reef within the quadrat area.
 - Count and measure all flat tree oysters separately (see oyster species composition below).

Figure B.4: Diagram depicting shell height from Baggett et al., 2014.

4. Reef footprint & area: GPS mapping (based on Baggett et al., 2014)
 - Set up the GPS unit appropriately to collect polygon data.

-
- To collect data, slowly walk along the edge of the reef collecting location data at 1 second intervals.
 - The reef edge is the outer extent of the reef where percent cover of reef material (live oyster or oyster shell) remaining above the sediment is equal or greater to 25% of substrate composition (Baggett et al., 2014; Janiak, 2021). For intertidal reefs, the reef edge is often submerged and should be assessed visually and/or by feel when walking. Reef substrate is made up of shell and is typically much harder than surrounding sediment.
 - For reef sites made up of multiple patches or reef modules, collect each patch or module as a separate polygon.
 - To ensure better GPS accuracy in the field:
 - Move slowly and always try to collect data at 1 second intervals.
 - Leave file open in field to get carrier data (even after data collection & moving) for more accuracy.
 - It may be useful to note the time, tide, and information about reef exposure and submergence.

5. Reef height (Baggett et al., 2014; Janiak, 2021)

- Visually assess the reef site and determine the highest areas or reef crest.
- Take 4 samples spread across the reef area at the 4 highest points.
 - For reef bars, this can be done by taking 4 measurements along the length of the crest.
 - For reef sites made up of multiple patches or modules, this can be done by dividing the site into 4 sections and selecting the highest point in each section.
- Have one person hold a string against the tallest oysters at a selected high point.
- Have a second person walk the other end of the string out to the reef edge and have a third person attach a line level to the middle of the string.
 - Reef edge is the outer extent of the reef where percent cover of reef material (live oyster or oyster shell) remaining above the sediment is equal or greater to 25% of substrate composition (Baggett et al., 2014; Janiak, 2021).
- Have the third person stand at the middle of the string line and give the second person (at the reef edge) directions to move the string up or down along the stadia rod until the level on the string line is balanced.
- Height measurements should be taken at the reef edge in the same general cardinal direction (offshore) for all 4 samples.
- It may be helpful to record GPS locations where reef height measurements were taken.

6. Oyster species composition

- Data regarding flat tree oysters should be collected during percent cover and density data collection.
- To collect data regarding presence and abundance of crested oyster (*Ostrea equestris*) collect 15 boxed oysters per reef site. Collect specimen between 15 and 40mm in shell height to target the size range of *O. equestris*.
 - Collect boxed oysters to ensure specimens recruited to reef site and are not shell-culch that were placed during restoration efforts.
- Take the specimen back to the lab, open the boxed oysters, and clean the interior shell surface.
- Examine the interior shell margins to identify oyster species.
 - Crested oyster will have chomata starting near umbo and growing along the shell margin.
 - Eastern oyster will NOT have chomata.

Eastern oyster (<i>Crassostrea virginica</i>)	Flat tree oyster (<i>Isognomon alatus</i>)	Crested oyster (<i>Ostrea equestris</i>)
<p>Most common and familiar oyster species</p> <p>Adductor scar usually purple</p> <p>Adults can grow to 250mm shell height</p>	<p>Attach by byssal threads</p> <p>Flattened square shaped umbo</p> <p>Tend to be relatively flat, thin, and broad</p> <p>Adults can grow to 95mm shell height</p>	<p><u>Chomata present (identifying character)</u></p> <p>Adductor muscle scar usually clear</p> <p>Some have zigzag pattern along shell edge where valves meet</p>

		Adults typically only grow to 40mm shell height
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Figure B.5: Key for identifying different species of oysters.

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Appendix C- Condition Index SOP

Crassostrea virginica Health and Condition Index Standard Operating Procedure

Jaworski & McCoy, July 2025

HEALTH & CONDITION:

For a quick assessment of oyster health, a condition index rating key developed by Quick & Mackin (1971) can be used. This particular condition index rating key scores oyster tissue from 1-9, with 1 indicating that oyster health is very good and 9 indicating oyster health is very poor (Table C.1).

Table C.1: Condition Index Rating Key

Condition Index Rating	#	Oyster Appearance
Very Good	1	Animal firm and filling shell cavity; coloration creamy white and evenly textured, usually ready to spawn.
Good	2	Not quite as firm or large as above; usually ready to spawn.
Good Minus	3	Coloration less opaque, often slightly yellow or gray.
Fair Plus	4	Animal distinctly not filling shell cavity; coloration often mottled, with blood vessels and muscle fibers showing through the more translucent epithelium.
Fair	5	Oyster well-developed but not opaque or tending toward white; grayish and translucent; flesh flaccid.
Fair Minus	6	Translucency is more pronounced.
Poor Plus	7	Oyster not well-developed, darker gray, often greenish; pericardial cavity clear; small portion of shell cavity filled.
Poor	8	Negative qualities are more accentuated.
Very Poor	9	Animal distinctly atrophied; coloration dark and uneven, very translucent; seldom more than a third of shell cavity occupied; adductor muscle often discolored and transparent even in the normally white sector.

However, a more quantitative assessment of oyster health includes using the condition index (CI) as a metric. In particular, this metric assesses the quality and yield of oysters by determining tissue fullness relative to the size of the shell. The CI of individual oysters can be calculated using Hopkin's formula (Hopkins, 1949; Lawrence & Scott, 1982):

$$CI = [DTW (g) \times 100] / [SCC (g)]$$

where DTW is the dry tissue weight of the oyster and SCC is the shell cavity capacity. The collected oyster specimen is cleaned, various morphometric data is taken (see Table C.2) and the oyster is shucked open. Once the oyster is shucked open, the oyster tissue is placed into a drying

oven at 68 °C for 24 hours (if assessing oyster tissue for disease in addition to condition index, refer to the assay protocol SOP on how to attain dry weight tissue and a sample for disease analysis). DTW is determined by weighing the oyster tissue in grams after 24 hours at 68 °C. In addition to drying the tissue, oyster shells should be dried overnight for at least 24 hours and individually weighed. To determine the SCC, a proxy will be used by subtracting the weight of the dried oyster shell from the total weight of the shell plus tissue. Indeed, both methods of determining the health and condition of oysters are simple and time-efficient, which could provide additional baseline information about oyster reefs with limited resource availability.

Table C.2: Sample metrics recommended for health and condition indexing of oysters.

Metric	Description
Oys_ID	ID of oyster specimen.
Region	Region where oysters were collected (e.g., SLE vs IRL)
Site_Name	Site where oysters were collected (e.g., ROSE, PEND)
Site_Type	Natural vs Artificial
Oys_CI_Rating	Condition index rating key # based on Quick & Mackin 1971 scale.
Shell_Length	Measurement A, Figure C.1.
Shell_Height	Measurement B, Figure C.1.
Shell_Width	Measurement C, Figure C.1.
Oys_Weight	Wet weight of oyster tissue and shell in grams.
Oys_Wet_Tissue	Wet weight of oyster tissue in grams.
Oys_Dry_Tissue	Dry weight of oyster tissue in grams.
Oys_Dry_Shell	Dry weight of oyster shell in grams.

Figure C.1: *Diagram of oyster shell measurements required. Adapted from Harvesting UF Field Trials (2018).*

REFERENCES & RESOURCES

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<https://doi.org/10.2307/1352213>

Appendix D- Perkinsus Marinus (Dermo) SOP

Perkinsus marinus Assay Protocol Standard Operating Procedure

Jaworski & McCoy, July 2025

Adapted from Maryland DNR and Rutgers

STANDARD ASSAY TO DIAGNOSE PERKINSUS MARINUS INFECTION

SOLUTION PREPARATION:

Table D.1: Supplies needed to create three solutions: Ray's Fluid Thioglycollate Medium, an antibiotic, and Lugol's iodine.

<i>Ray's Fluid Thioglycollate Medium</i>	<i>Antibiotic Solution</i>	<i>Lugol's Iodine Solution</i>
22 g sodium chloride	0.33 g streptomycin sulfate	4 g potassium iodide
29.3 g fluid thioglycollate medium	0.159 g benzylpenicillin	2 g of iodine
1 L distilled water	500 mL deionized water	100 mL distilled water

Ray's Fluid Thioglycollate Medium (RFTM):

1. In a beaker with a stir-bar, create a mixture of 22 g of sodium chloride (NaCl), 29.3 g of dehydrated Fluid Thioglycollate Medium (FTM), and 1 L of distilled water that is heated until the medium dissolves.
2. Allow the RFTM to cool and then dispense 5 mL into 10 mL (provides expansion room for heated RFTM) autoclavable culture tubes.
3. Leave culture tube screw caps on loosely and autoclave RFTM at 121 °C / 15psi for 15 minutes.
4. Allow culture tubes to cool (in a sanitary environment) and close screw caps on tightly.
5. Store RFTM in dark conditions (e.g., wrap tube rack in aluminum foil) at room temperature until use.

Antibiotic Solution:

1. Add 0.33 g of streptomycin sulfate, 0.159 g of benzylpenicillin, and 500 mL of sterile (autoclaved at 121 °C / 15psi for 30 minutes), deionized water in a storage jar.
2. Shake lightly until all powder is dissolved.
3. Store antibiotic solution in the refrigerator until use.

Lugol's Iodine Solution:

1. Dissolve 4 g potassium iodide (KI) and 2 g iodine (I) in 100 mL of distilled water.

2. Allow the solution to stand for 24 hours and then filter the solution to remove any particles.
3. Keep the solution stored in a dark bottle at room temperature until use. If stored for longer periods, filter to remove particles occasionally.

TISSUE COLLECTION & ANALYSIS:

1. Using sterile dissecting tools between specimens, excise a piece of mantle tissue from each specimen.
2. Place the tissue in an individually labeled 10 mL culture tube that contains 5 mL of RFTM that was previously prepared.
3. Add approximately 0.5 mL of the antibiotic solution (streptomycin sulfate and benzylpenicillin) that was previously prepared in the 10 mL culture tube containing the tissue.
4. Recap and invert the culture tube to submerge the entire piece of tissue in the RFTM.
5. Place the culture tubes in dark conditions at room temperature for a minimum of 5 days and no more than 7 days.
6. After the incubation period, using sterile tools, remove the tissue from the RFTM and place it on a microscope slide.
7. Macerate and tease apart the tissue sample to ensure even staining with Lugol’s iodine solution.
8. Add 1-2 drops (more as needed) of Lugol’s iodine solution that was previously prepared to the tissue sample and cover the microscope slide with a cover slip.
9. Examine the slide microscopically for *Perkinsus marinus* hypnospores and assign a semi-quantitative scale of infection intensity (Table D.2).

Table D.2: *Semi-quantitative scale of infection intensity. Adapted from Quick and Mackin by Craight et al. (1989).*

<i>Infection Intensity</i>	<i>Description</i>
0.00	No hypnospores present.
0.33	1-10 hypnospores.
0.67	11-74 hypnospores.
1.00	75-125 hypnospores.
1.33	>125 hypnospores but <25% of tissue is hypnospores.
1.67	<25% of tissue is hypnospores.
2.00	25% of tissue is hypnospores.
2.33	>25% but way less <50% of tissue is hypnospores.
2.67	>25% but <50% of tissue is hypnospores.
3.00	50% of tissue is hypnospores.

3.33	>50% but way less <75% of tissue is hypnospores.
3.67	>50% but <75% of tissue is hypnospores.
4.00	75% of tissue is hypnospores.
4.33	>75% but way <100% of tissue is hypnospores.
4.67	>75% of tissue is hypnospores but some tissue is still visible.
5.00	Nearly 100% of tissue is hypnospores.

Table 3. Sample metrics recommended for quantifying *Perkinsus* spp. disease in oysters.

<i>Metric</i>	<i>Description</i>
Oys_ID	ID of oyster specimen.
Region	Region where oysters were collected (e.g., SLE vs IRL).
Site_Name	Site where oysters were collected (e.g., Pend, FtPierce).
Site_Type	Natural vs Artificial.
Prevalence	Proportion infected (0: uninfected; 1: infected).
Hypnospores	# of hypnospores.
Inf_Intens	Infection intensity # based on the semi-quantitative scale.
Mean_Inf_Intens	Mean of infection intensity for all oyster tissue (0 – 5)
Inf_Intens_Ind	Mean of infection intensity for only infected oyster tissue (0.33 – 5)
Perc_Lethal_Inf	Proportion of samples with infection intensities = 5.

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Appendix E- Wave Gauge SOP

Wave Gauge Development and Deployment Standard Operating Procedure

Original procedure adapted from the following resources:

- Dr. Bret Webb's Github page: <https://github.com/bwebb-southal/feathergauge>
- Temple, N., Webb, B., Sparks, E., Linhoss, A. 2020. Low-Cost Pressure Gauges for Measuring Water Waves. *Journal of Coastal Research* 36(3), 661-667. <https://doi.org/10.2112/JCOASTRES-D-19-00118.1>
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- <https://coastal.msstate.edu/waves>
- Construction video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sRoGt_vNaXw&t=2269s

These resources contain more detail and troubleshooting procedures that are not available in this SOP. Please consult them for additional resources.

EQUIPMENT CHECKLIST

Materials for Wave Gauge Construction

- Adafruit Feather 32u4 Adalogger
- Precision RTC FeatherWing
- Short Feather Male Headers
- Short Feather Female Headers
- CR 1220 coin cell battery
- Blue Robotics Bar02 Ultra High Resolution 10m Depth/Pressure Sensor
- 4400 mAh Li Ion Battery
- JST GH 4-pin
- Wire (bundle pack 28 awg)
- USB Charger Station Block with Rapid Charging with 10 ports
- Micro USB Cable 1ft - charging cable
- USB-A to Micro USB Charging Cable
- Adafruit MicroSD card
- Soldering iron
- Leaded solder
- Solder removal device
- Wire cutters
- Wire strippers
- Shrink wrap for wires
- Vise for soldering

Materials for Housing Construction

- Concrete block (a half concrete block can be used in low wave energy environments)
- Yellow Rope and small buoy
- PVC (10' X 1.5") pipe cut to fit the gauge
- PVC conduit clamp/strap- 2 inch

-
- Galvanized cement screws - we have Tapcon
 - Masonry drillbit - we have Tapcon
 - Strong-Tie #6 x 1/2-in Stainless steel Exterior Wood screws
 - A plastic tag to label the wave gauge as a research sensor and who it belongs to (if gauges are going into a high traffic or public area)
 - Silicone Caulk
 - PVC cap 1.5"
 - Gripper 1-1/2 in. Plastic Mechanical Test Plug
 - 10' X 2" PVC to hold gauges - cut to fit the concrete blocks
 - PVC socket cap 1.5"
 - PVC male adapter 1.5"
 - PVC solvent cement
 - Velcro straps

Programming Adafruit Motherboard Checklist

- Constructed motherboards with batteries
- Constructed pipe with pressure sensor
- Computer with installed Arduino IDE

Deployment Checklist

- Preassembled Wave Gauges
 - programmed Arduino board
 - Micro SD card
 - Coin battery CR2032
 - Charged lithium battery[1]
 - pressure sensor and pvc pipe (labelled with number for deployment)
 - PVC cap to go over the pressure sensor
 - Wingnut test seal
- Micro USB to USB/USB-C Cord to connect to laptop/tablet
- Laptop or tablet
- Micro SD card reader and necessary port adapter
- Multi outlet usb Charger to charge batteries

Figure E.1: Depiction of the pvc pipe and wave gauge components.

WAVE GAUGE CONSTRUCTION (Figure E.1)

These are basic instructions for putting together the wave gauges. More extensive instructions can be found Nigel Temple's and Bret Webb's wave gauge construction video (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sRoGt_vNaXw&t=2269s) although the video uses older specifications than detailed in these instructions.

1. Stack one feather board on top of the other (coin slot feather board on top) using male and female pins with short pins going into the feather board on both sides.
2. Solder the headers to the feather board starting with the top feather board (coin cell battery side). If you make a mistake you can use a wick or solder removal plunger to reheat the solder and remove it from the board.
3. Solder the headers to the other of the feather board.
4. Solder wires to the feather board
5. Gentle pull apart feather boards making sure not to bend the headers
6. Strip one side of wires (6 inch wires or so).
7. Solder wires to the GND pin (closest to 3v pin; black wire), 3v pin (red wire), SDA pin (white wire), SCL pin (yellow wire).
8. Brain wires together, running the wires out opposite the side with the SD card
9. Reconnect the stacking headers and both sides of the feather board put the shrink wraps onto the wires.
10. Attach (solder) the wires to the JST GH 4-pin (watch video for more information)
11. Put the shrink wrap over the connects with the wires and use heat to shrink them down
12. Then move on to placing the pressure sensor in the PVC cap (unthreaded). Drill a small hole just big enough to seat the pressure sensor in the PVC cap.

-
13. Cut the thread off of the PVC male adapter and using marine glue, glue the thread on top of the PVC cap. Let dry
 14. Using epoxy putty, place the pressure sensor in the PVC cap, string the wires through the hole and ensuring a water tight seal. Make sure the pressure sensor is flat.
 15. Using clear epoxy, make sure that the connection between the pressure sensor and hole in the pvc pipe is sealed. DO NOT get epoxy on the sensitive membrane of the sensor.
 16. Also use the epoxy or marine glue to seal the connection between the cap and thread.
 17. Let dry
 18. Using PVC cement to connect the cap to the pvc pipe that will contain the gauge. Run the wires through the pipe.
 19. Once dry, add clear epoxy or marine glue along the junction of the cap with the pipe to ensure the seal.
 20. Using a ruler that has been cut to fit in the pipe, secure the battery and the featherboard to the ruler using velcro straps.
 21. Drill several holes in the threaded PVC cap and attach to the thread on the top of the PVC gauge.
 22. Attach the red wing nut test plug to the other side of the PVC.

PROGRAMMING ADAFRUIT FEATHER BOARDS

These are the basic instructions for programming the Adafruit featherboards. More extensive instructions can be found at Bret Webb's Github account, here: <https://github.com/bwebb-southal/feathergauge>

1. Download Arduino IDE
2. Set up specifications for the Adafruit boards under the preferences and the board manager
3. Download the appropriate libraries
4. Add the logger code sketch downloaded from the Github project to the Arduino Sketchbook
5. Make sure the battery on the gauge is charged
6. Connect the motherboard to the computer
7. Open the sketch through the arduino software: See github description
8. Compile and upload the sketch to the adafruit board
9. Open the serial monitor in the Arduino IDE and check to make sure the data and time are correct.
10. If date/time are not correct, follow instructions for troubleshooting the clock.
11. Choose the type of logging you want (delayed start, burst sampling, etc). and then upload that sketch to the logger.
12. Define the parameter values needed for the project.
13. Allow the gauge to sample for about 60 seconds.
14. Remove the Micro SD card and connect to your computer through port or adapters.
15. Check your data file and make sure that the date and time and pressure are correct.
16. Remove the datafiles that have downloaded and put the Micro SD card back into the board.

DEPLOYMENT

You can find more information about the deployment of wave gauges at Bret Webb's github account, here: <https://github.com/bwebb-southal/feathergauge>

1. Plug in the battery
2. Confirm LED flashing* (as of versions labeled _v1):
 - a. rapid start, continuous sampling: solid green for about the first ~10 seconds then no other LEDs
 - b. Rapid start, burst sampling: solid green during burst sampling; solid red during sleep interval
 - c. delayed start, continuous sampling: flashing red for ~20 seconds before start time; solid green for about the first ~10 seconds of continuous sampling
 - d. delayed start, burst sampling: flashing red for ~20 seconds before start time; solid green during burst sampling; solid red while sleeping in between bursts
3. Insert components into gauge housing along with a small desiccant pack
4. Allow to sample** in atmospheric pressure for at least 1-2 minutes
5. Place all prepared gauges in a bucket filled with your seawater (preferably from your deployment location but freshwater will do) and allow to sample** for at least 1-2 minutes. Ensure all sensors are oriented similarly (sensor at the bottom of the bucket).
6. Deploy sensor making sure you keep depth attenuation in mind... see guidance on the Webb Github page.
7. Deploy the gauge horizontally or vertically, and if vertically do so with sensor port pointing downward (Figure E.2).

Notes for Deployment:

*In step 2: if you would like to conserve more battery power, disabling the LED flashing is a fairly simple task. Any/all commands labeled “digitalWrite(---)” within the void loop() structure can be commented out with no impact to the code operation whatsoever. To comment (i.e., disable) out the LED blinking, simply place your cursor on the line of code (to the left of) containing the active digitalWrite(8, xxx) or digitalWrite(13, xxx) command, then select Edit / Comment/Uncomment from the Arduino IDE menu. If the line is active, it will become inactive, you'll see two “//” before the statement, and the text will turn gray. To reactivate that line of code, either remove the “//” or select Edit / Comment/Uncomment again and the line of code will become active once again.

**In steps 4-5: this only makes sense if you are using the rapid start version of the logger code sketches. If you are using the rapid start code with burst sampling, make sure you are logging atmospheric and bucket test pressures during your burst interval (refer to LED flashing codes above for reference). If you are using the delayed start version of the code sketches, it may not be possible to sample atmospheric or bucket test pressures prior to deployment. If that is the case, it is strongly recommended performing this at the end of your deployment (before removing the battery). The atmospheric and bucket test pressure samples allow you to perform minor corrections to ensure consistent measurement values across your gauges. The inexpensive pressure sensors seem to have small offsets that, while not

necessary, could be advantageous to correct by comparing their values under static conditions.

Figure E.2: Deployment of wave gauges behind a restored oyster reef.

POST-DEPLOYMENT

You can find more information about the deployment of wave gauges at Bret Webb's github account, here: <https://github.com/bwebb-southal/feathergauge>.

When retrieving your wave gauge:

1. Do not open gauge before cleaning thoroughly
2. Submerge gauge in a bucket of warm water mixed with distilled white vinegar (dish soap optional, but not necessary)
3. If gauges are especially dirty, consider adding baking soda as this will combine with the vinegar to produce strong agitation and fizzing (definitely do not use dish soap here)
4. **DO NOT touch the gel membrane inside of the pressure sensor**
5. Remove from cleaning bath and wipe dry

-
6. Remove cap
 7. Check for signs of moisture
 8. Remove internal components
 9. Disconnect battery
 10. Remove micro SD card

POST-PROCESSING

You can find more information about the deployment of wave gauges at Bret Webb's github account, here: <https://github.com/bwebb-southal/feathergauge>.

The gauge data will be saved to CSV files on the microsd card. Post-processing the pressure data can be done in a variety of ways. Bret Webb has posted some example post-processing scripts written in MATLAB on his GitHub page. If you don't have access to MATLAB you might find your own alternative method for processing the data. We have posted examples in R on the following our Github Project Page. Note that the pressure values are absolute, so you need to subtract out atmospheric pressure. Ideally, you would have an atmospheric reference nearby so that you have a time-series of data, but in a pinch you can use an average/estimated value of atmospheric pressure. Each millibar of atmospheric pressure corresponds to (approximately) 1 cm of water height change.

Steps:

1. Insert microsd card into your computer
2. Save the files to your computer
3. Run the MATLAB post-processing scripts or process using your own code

TROUBLESHOOTING

You can find more information about the deployment of wave gauges at Bret Webb's github account, here: <https://github.com/bwebb-southal/feathergauge>.

1. *My board isn't recognized by Arduino IDE:* make sure you are using a power+data cable... many micro USB cables are power only... if the device is not recognized as a com port under device manager (windows) then you're probably using a power only cable.
2. *My board isn't recognized by Arduino IDE and I am sure that I am using an appropriate power+data cable:* try resetting the bootloader on the feather logger board (see below).
3. *I need to reset my bootloader:* you'll need access to the small black reset button located near the micro USB plug on top of the board. With the board plugged in, open the blink sketch found in File / Examples / Basics / Blink. Click the compile/upload "arrow" icon. Immediately double tap the reset button. This should resolve the issue. You may need to do this a few times.
4. *My date/time are incorrect:* refer to 2 and 3 in the Deployment Preparation section above.
5. *My logger isn't working correctly:* try uploading something simple like File / Examples / Basics / Blink. Does that work? If not, there's likely an issue with your board. If yes, see below.
6. *My logger still isn't working:*
 - a. Check your microsd card. Is it installed correctly? Are you using the recommended 8gb

microsd card? If not, this may be the issue. The logger cannot handle large microsd cards.

b. Check your wiring.

c. Perform a continuity check.

7. *My logger is writing to the microsd card, but the values don't make sense.*

a. Check your wiring... make sure you did not reverse the SCL and SDA wires.

b. Try using the simple sketch provided by the MS5837 pressure sensor manufacturer by going to File / Examples / BlueRobotics MS5837 Library / MS5837_example. Before uploading, you'll need to change one line in the code. Refer to the line with...

```
sensor.setModel(MS5837::MS5837_30BA);
```

and change the `_30BA` to `_02BA` as follows...

```
sensor.setModel(MS5837::MS5837_02BA);
```

then open the Serial Monitor and see if the values make sense.

open for addressing future issues...

Appendix F- Sediment Characteristics SOP

Sediment Plate and Sediment Characteristics Standard Operating Procedure

Original procedure adapted from the following resources:

- Ewers Lewis and McGlathery 2023: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2023.1232619>
- ASTM D613-04(2009)e1: Standard Test Methods for Particle-Size Distribution (Graduation) of Soils using Sieve Analysis
- Bulk Density and Loss of Ignition Protocol from the [Zimmer Lab](#).

Updated and edited by Anna Braswell and Maylet Perez, School of Forest Fisheries and Geomatics Sciences, University of Florida

Contact: Anna Braswell - a.braswell@ufl.edu

Goal: This protocol is to assess sediment accretion in intertidal areas and sediment characteristics from sediment cores.

EQUIPMENT CHECKLIST

Corer Construction

- Plexiglass tube (we use a rigid polycarbonate round tube that is clear and 104 mm inside diameter)
- Wing nut test plug ([Home Depot link](#))
- 2 foot PVC pipe
- 2.5 foot wooden rod
- Socket - we used $\frac{3}{8}$ inch
- Coupling nut (we used $\frac{3}{8}$ inch)
- Marine glue
- Wood or metal file

Initial Field Deployment

- 4 inch black acrylic discs (0.04 inch thick)
- A probe ($\frac{1}{8}$ inch or smaller, metal, 3 feet long metal rod)
- 4 PVC pipe pieces per sediment plate or some other way to mark the plate
- Ruler
- Field notebook

Sediment Core Collection

- Gallon size plastic bags
- Ruler
- 4 in test cap ([Home Depot Link](#))
- Sharpie
- Cooler

Sediment Plate Monitoring

- Probe (see above)

-
- 4 in test cap ([Home Depot Link](#))
 - Field note book

Analysis of Sediment Characteristics in Lab

- Latex gloves
- High temperature mitts
- Tongs
- Aluminum tins (weigh boats)
- Pencil
- Metal Spatula
- Chem Wipes
- Fire Bricks/Shelves
- Desiccator
- Drying oven
- Muffle furnace
- Balance (four decimal places)
- Pair of Tweezers
- Mortar and Pestle

Analysis of Sediment Size Characteristics through Sieving

- Set of nesting sieves (we use a Standard Sieve Set from mesh 4-250 - see Figure F.3)
- Oven dried soil samples
- Balance with three significant differences
- Plastic bags or whirl packs to store sieved samples
- Container for weighing the sediment samples on the balance
- A brush to wipe out any remaining sediment in the sieves
- Mortar and pestle

CORER CONSTRUCTION (Figure F.1)

1. Take plexiglass tube and decide which side will be pressed into the sediment. For this side, take the file and file an sharp edge by filing on the interior edge of the tube.
2. Cut the pvc pipe with a small slit to match the wing nut of the seal.
3. Attach the coupling nut to the test seal above the wing nut and tighten.
4. Use marine glue to attach socket onto wooden rod. Make sure that it is level.

Figure F.1: Components of the sediment core setup and the sediment plate.

SEDIMENT PLATE DEPLOYMENT

1. Push water-tightening soil corer at least 5 cm into the ground behind and near the reef as level as possible.
2. Push down the seal and twist using the pvc pipe and socket rod to create a vacuum.
3. Carefully lift the core to allow a sediment plate to be placed under the layer of soil. Be sure to keep the bottom of the corer level and underwater while the sediment plate goes in.
4. With the core directly over the plate, release the seal.
5. Mark the plate's location with poles on four corners.
6. Measure the layer of sediment on the plate using a thin rod and a ruler. Stick the rod into the sediment until it reaches resistance. Mark where the rod meets the sediment. Measure the length of the rod that was under the sediment and record it in a notebook. Take measurements in 3 different spots on the plate and use the average as your measurement.

SEDIMENT CORE COLLECTION (Figure F.2)

1. Push water-tightening soil corer to 5 cm into the ground behind and near the reef as level as possible.
2. Push down the seal and twist using the pvc pipe and socket rod to create a vacuum.
3. Carefully lift the core to allow the cap to be placed on the end of the corer. Be sure to keep the bottom of the corer level and underwater while the cap goes on.
4. Release sediment core into a labelled gallon size bag.

Figure F.2: Taking a sediment core using the plexiglass corer and seal/pvc set up.

SEDIMENT PLATE MONITORING

1. Find sediment plate.
2. Use rod to measure the layer of sediment on top of the plate: Stick rod into the sediment until it reaches resistance. Mark where the rod meets the sediment. Measure the length of the rod that was under the sediment and record it in a notebook. Take measurements in 3 different spots on the plate and use the average as your measurement.

Analysis of Sediment Characteristics: Organic Matter and Soil Composition

BULK DENSITY MEASUREMENTS

-
1. Put on **latex** gloves to keep skin oils from transferring to the tins.
 2. Get an aluminum tin - label the tin on the tab with tweezers, etching the number into the tab. Pick a unique number and record that number and the sample information on the datasheet
 1. NOTE: Etching the numbers onto the tin is crucial, regular sharpie will burn off in the muffle furnace.
 3. Weigh tin in balance and record weight on the datasheet.
 4. Make sure the drying oven is set at 100° C
 5. Place the sediment core sample (of known volume) into the aluminum tin and reweigh. Record weight on datasheet. This is the wet weight of the sample (WW_{sample}).
 6. Place the samples in the drying oven in an organized fashion (numerical order: left to right, front to back).
 7. Leave samples in the drying oven for at least 12 hours.
 8. Use tongs or mitts to remove the tins from drying oven – tins will be warm (see step 9-a)
 9. Place tins in dessicator to cool.
 1. If there are no desiccators available the samples come right out of the drying oven and be weighed. Please be careful - tins will be hot.
 10. Once cool, weigh again with latex gloves on. This is the dry weight of the sample (DW_{sample}).

LOSS ON IGNITION MEASUREMENTS

1. Place the sample in Mortar and Pestle and gently grind up sample until a uniform powder.
2. Re-weigh tin boat and record.
3. Carefully sweep the sample back into tin. Use a brush if necessary. Make the sure mortar and pestle are clean between samples.
 - There will be residual sample that gets stuck to the mortar and pestle, make sure they are cleaned thoroughly -- to do this use a damp paper towel to wipe any dirt that is left over. Be sure to dry everything before the next sample is ground.
4. Weigh sample and tin again and record.
5. Set the muffle furnace to 500° C
6. Place samples in the furnace in an organized fashion and leave the furnace overnight or for 12-15 hours.
7. Let the furnace cool with samples inside of it.
8. Remove the tins using latex gloves.
9. Weigh tins and sample and record on the datasheet. Be sure to weigh quickly once out of the muffle furnace. The samples will start absorbing water quickly. If you don't have time to weigh the after pulling the samples out of the muffle furnace, place the samples in a warm drying oven or dessicator.
10. When the final weight of the samples is recorded they can be discarded.

CLEAN-UP

1. Scrub tins in bin with soap and tap water to remove all baked on residue
2. Rinse with DI water
3. Place washed tins in furnace at 550°C – for 2 hours

-
4. Remove and place in storage

CALCULATIONS

1. Determine gravimetric soil water content (SWC, g water / g dry soil) of section subsample:

$$\text{SWC} = (\text{WW}_{\text{sample}} - \text{DW}_{\text{sample}} [3] / \text{DW}_{\text{sample}})$$

2. Calculate total bulk density (g/cm³) of soil sample:

$$\text{BD}_{\text{total}} = \text{DW}_{\text{sample}} / V$$

where:

$$V = \text{volume of core section in cm}^3 = \text{cylindrical volume} = (\pi) (r^2) h$$

3. Final equation for Organic Matter determination:

$$\%OM = \frac{\text{pre - ignition weight (g)} - \text{post - ignition weight (g)}}{\text{pre - ignition weight (g)}} \times 100\%$$

SIEVING FOR SEDIMENT SIZE CHARACTERIZATION

This is a method for determining the weight of each sample at seven different sediment size thresholds based on the ASTM Sieving standard – Single sieve set. Please see Table 2 and Table 3 in the ASTM D613-04(2009)e1: Standard Test Methods for Particle-Size Distribution (Graduation) of Soils using Sieve Analysis for determining the minimum and maximum mass requirements for sieving samples.

1. Use samples that have been dried in the drying oven and either stored there until sieving or put in a dessicator (see above oven drying). Make sure that all aggregations are broken up. If not, use a mortar and pestle to break up aggregations.
2. Weigh the sample on a balance using a tared container. Record the weight of the whole sample
3. Using the nesting sieve set, place the sample in the largest mesh sleeve. Cover the stack of sieves with a lid.
4. Shake the sieves either with a mechanical shaker or by hand for a set amount of time. All sediment should have time to make it through the appropriate sieve, making sure that small grained sediment makes it into the bottom sieve.

-
5. Working from largest to smallest, take each sieve and place the sample into a tared container on the balance. Weigh sample and record weight.
 6. Repeat for each sieve, wiping out and re-taring the container in between each sample.
 7. Use the weight to determine the proportion of the sample at each particle size.
 8. Analyze sieving data in Excel and R using codes provided as part of the Sediment Analysis SOP. (See our Project Github Account)

Figure F.3: Assembling sieve stack from coarse to fine mesh; pan at the bottom.

Appendix G- Habitat Tray SOP

Habitat Tray Standard Operating Procedure

EQUIPMENT CHECKLIST

Habitat tray construction

- Polypropylene trays: 0.25m x 0.5m x 0.10m: <https://www.katom.com/144-HBR258151.html>
 - 3 trays per reef site
- Polyethylene mesh: 1/4in openings = 6.35mm: <https://www.industrialnetting.com/xv1170-48-50-4-foot-black-cage-net.html>
- Zip ties
- Scissors

Initial field deployment

- Assembled habitat trays (3 per reef)
- Gloves
- Trowels
- Tip: for high wave energy sites bring
 - Rebar (2ft x 1/8in, 2 pieces per box)
 - Chicken wire (cut to cover top of habitat tray)
 - Metal mallet
- Permits/SALs (laminated)

Tray recovery

- Gloves
- Plastic bin (large enough to fit habitat tray contents)
- Datasheets (printed on waterproof paper)
- Pencils
- Clipboards
- White 5-gallon buckets (1 for each habitat tray)
- Bucket lids (1 for each bucket)
- Bubblers (1 for each bucket)
- Extra batteries for bubblers
- 1 5-gallon bucket of clean shell (for 3 reef sites)
- Tweezers
- Small containers with holes (to isolate sensitive or aggressive organisms)
- Laminated paper

-
- Dry-erase marker
 - Duct tape
 - Sharpies
 - Permits/SALs (laminated)

Tray processing

- Electric bubblers (1 per bucket)
- 5-gallon buckets (at least 1 per site)
- Duct tape
- Sharpie
- Datasheets (printed on waterproof paper)
- 1mm sieve
- Glass dishes
- Waterproof paper
- Camera
- Tweezers
- Gloves
- Optivisors and magnification tools
- Dissecting microscope
- Permits/SALs (laminated)

Note: Collection of live organisms described in the following procedure requires a Special Activities License (SAL) from FWC in the state of Florida.

HABITAT TRAY CONSTRUCTION

1. Assemble habitat trays (Figure G.1)
 - Cut polyethylene mesh to cover interior of polypropylene trays
 - Attach polypropylene mesh to interior of polyethylene tray with zip ties
 - Ensure mesh covers all openings in polypropylene tray

Figure G.1: Image of assembled habitat tray.

INITIAL FIELD DEPLOYMENT

1. Determine suitable locations within the reef site to deploy 3 habitat trays (Janiak, 2021; Jud & Layman, 2020)
 - Trays should be deployed at mid-elevation of the reef site, maximizing inter-tray distance while minimizing depth and substrate variation.
 - Keep replicates several meters apart from each other.
 - For sites comprised of multiple patches or reef modules, consider the entire site as one reef & place trays at mid reef elevation.
 - Try to deploy trays in areas of the reef site with high live oyster cover.
2. Place each habitat tray into the reef substrate (Figure G.2) (Janiak, 2021)
 - Excavate a portion of the reef so the top of the habitat tray is flush with the reef surface.
 - To keep the disturbed area to a minimum, make the excavation just large enough to fit the habitat tray.
 - Place the habitat tray into the depression and fill the tray with the excavated material.
 - Ensure that oyster density inside the box resembles the surrounding reef.
 - Keep in mind that for reefs with lower cover, including an excessive amount of material can inflate counts.
 - For restored reefs made of restoration material (plastic, metal, concrete, etc), you may need to disarticulate the synthetic material to place the tray.
 - For high wave energy sites, use rebar and chicken wire to stabilize the habitat tray and contents (Figure G.2).

- o 2 pieces of 2ft x 1/8in rebar can be inserted into habitat tray and secured approximately 1ft into below substrate. Approximately 1ft should be above substrate and 1ft below substrate.
- o Chicken wire can be secured to the top of the habitat tray and rebar using zipties to secure the chicken wire and hold the habitat tray contents in place.
- o Tip: habitat trays can become more easily dislodged at sites with low sediment content, large fetch, and heavy boat wakes.

Figure G.2: (Left) Habitat tray placed into reef substrate; (Right) Habitat tray placed into reef substrate and secured with chicken wire and rebar.

TRAY RECOVERY

1. Prepare collection bucket for each habitat tray.
 - For each reef site, label 3 5-gallon white buckets with the site name and habitat tray number using duct tape and a sharpie (e.g. REEF tray 1)
 - Put some clean oyster shell in each labeled bucket and fill the bucket with water from the site. Clean oyster shell is used to help alleviate stress and provide shelter for organisms during processing.
2. Collect habitat trays (Janiak, 2021).
 - After a 2-month deployment, recover habitat trays by swiftly lifting the habitat tray off the reef and immediately place it into a larger plastic tray. Bring the plastic working tray to the boat.
3. Carefully pick through the habitat tray material within the working tray. Collect all motile invertebrates (with an adult size over 5mm) by placing organisms into the appropriately labeled bucket. Each habitat tray should have its own bucket.
 - Spend extra time with oyster clusters as target species can be difficult to find, but do not break apart oyster clumps.

-
- The focus is on mobile invertebrates and fish with adult sizes > 5mm.
 - Fish, large crabs, or other sensitive organisms can be counted and identified in the field and released. If a sensitive organism needs to be brought back to the lab, place the organism in a small container with holes and place the container into the appropriate bucket with water from the site.
 - Very small and/or sessile invertebrates (i.e. amphipods, sponges, barnacles, ascidians) can be noted if present, but counting these individuals is impractical and can lead to flawed data.
4. Ensure the bucket is appropriately labeled with correct reef code and tray number.
 5. Secure bucket with lid and start bubbler. Bring buckets back to the lab.

TRAY PROCESSING

1. Select a bucket and fill out data sheet with corresponding reef code and habitat tray number (bucket should be labeled).
2. Sort through each bucket to enumerate organisms, identifying and grouping individuals to lowest taxonomic group efficiently (typically family).
 - Scoop out clean shells and organisms. Inspect shell and place it into a 5-gallon discard bucket. Sort organisms into separate trays based on lowest possible taxonomic group.
 - Once all clean shell and the majority of organisms have been removed, pour the remainder of the water through a sieve, pouring the water into the discard bucket and catching remaining organisms in the sieve.
3. Continue sorting until all organisms have been grouped. Then enumerate the number of individuals in each group. Take care to ensure all organisms have been enumerated and recorded.
4. Photograph sorted groups of organisms and include labels with the organism name, reef code, and tray number (Figure G.3). Take special care to photograph organisms you wish to identify later, taking photos from a variety of angles.
5. Make sure every organism in the bucket has been tallied!
6. Once all organisms have been processed, all organisms can be added to the clean shell and water in the discard bucket.
7. Return all specimen to the oyster reef site within 48 hours, or according to the timeline specified in the Special Activities License.

Figure G.3: Labeled photos of organisms.

References

Janiak, D. (2021). *MarineGEO oyster reef habitat monitoring protocol*. Tennenbaum Marine Observatories Network, MarineGEO, Smithsonian Institution.
<https://doi.org/10.25573/serc.14714328.v1>

Appendix H- Water Quality SOP

Water Quality (HOBO U-24 Logger) Standard Operating Procedure

EQUIPMENT CHECKLIST

Initial deployment

- YSI (calibrated)
- Field notebook
- Pencils
- 4ft 1inch PVC poles (1 per site)
- Large zipties (3 per logger)
- Rubber mallet
- Electrical tape
- Pantyhose
- Handheld GPS (Trimble, RTK, etc)

Data offload and maintenance

- YSI (calibrated)
- Gloves
- Wire cutters
- Paint scraper
- Computer
- HOBOLogger docking station
- USB
- Container of soap solution (several drops of dish detergent in container of tap water)
- Container of vinegar solution (white vinegar mixed with freshwater)
- Container of clean or distilled water
- Clean cotton swabs
- Toothbrush
- Q-tips
- Towels

Find more information on the HOBO conductivity logger here:

<https://www.onsetcomp.com/sites/default/files/resources-documents/16844-G%20U24-002-C%20Manual.pdf>

INITIAL DEPLOYMENT

Launching the conductivity logger

1. Start HOBOWare & connect logger to the computer.
 - Connect shuttle to logger by aligning components.
 - Press lever to start.
1. Verify the status
2. Launch logger
 - Name logger based on site.
 - Select range: select low and high range for estuarine sites (variable salinity).
 - Set sampling interval to 1hr.
 - Set sampling start time and date (EST) based on field plan. Note: Logger can also be launched in the field immediately before deployment.
 - Should read: “Launch successful” at bottom of screen.
 - When logger is programmed but has not started logging, a red light should blink every 8 seconds.

Prep logger to mitigate fouling (Figure H.1)

1. Prep loggers for deployment by wrapping body of logger in electrical tape.
 - Start at bottom of logger and wrap electrical tape around logger working up to the top.
2. Wrap top of logger (sensor) with pantyhose.
3. Cut pantyhose into small pieces and use pieces to cover top of the salinity logger. Attach the salinity logger using electrical tape.

Figure H.1: Datalogger wrapped in electrical tape and pantyhose to mitigate fouling.

Calibrate YSI

1. Calibrate YSI within 24 hours before use and conduct post-calibration within 24 hours after use.

Deploy logger

1. Deploy 4ft 1inch PVC pole by pounding the pole 2ft into the sediment using a rubber mallet.
 - Approximately 2ft should be below the sediment, and 2ft exposed above the sediment.
2. Attach HOBologger to anchoring system.
 - Use 3 large zipties to secure the HOBologger a few inches above the sediment.
 - The logger should stay submerged at all times.
 - 1 ziptie should be through the hole in top of logger, and 2 around the body of logger.
 - Make sure sensor facing away from PVC.
3. Allow HOBologger to stabilize (approximately 15 minutes).
4. Collect location data of salinity logger with handheld GPS (to ensure logger can be found at a later date).
5. Take calibration reading (Figure H.2):
 - Place YSI probes so that it is close to HOBologger but not touching.
 - Ensure there are no air bubbles under the pantyhose near the HOBologger sensor.

-
- Record temperature and conductivity using YSI.
 - Ensure to record the values, time, and location in water quality field notebook. Recording additional water quality metrics such as dissolved oxygen and pH may be beneficial.
 - Ensure to complete post-calibration within 24 hours.

Figure H.2: Researcher taking YSI calibration reading.

DATA OFFLOAD AND MAINTENANCE

1. Before entering the field, calibrate the YSI.
 - Calibrate YSI within 24 hours before use and conduct post-calibration within 24 hours after use.
2. After arriving at site, locate the HOBO logger & take a YSI reading.
 - Place YSI meter so that it is close to HOBO logger but not touching.
 - Measure temperature and actual conductivity using YSI.
 - Ensure to record the values, **time**, and location in water quality field notebook. Recording additional water quality metrics such as dissolved oxygen and pH may be beneficial.
1. Remove the logger and remove some biofouling.

-
- Remove logger from PVC pole by cutting zipties using wire cutters.
 - Remove biofouling from logger by taking off electrical tape.
 - Use a paint scraper to remove fouling from the PVC pole.
2. Plug HOBO logger into docking station, read out data, and save the data file (Figure H.3).
 - Save a secondary copy of the data to an USB.

Figure H.3: Researcher connecting HOBO datalogger to docking station.

3. Launch logger
 - Select range: select low and high range for estuarine sites (variable salinity).
 - Set sampling interval to 1hr.
 - Set sampling start time and date (EST). Set start time for approximately 20 minutes later, providing time to clean the datalogger and redeploy.
 - Should read: “Launch successful” at bottom of screen.
 - When logger is programmed but has not started logging, a red light should blink every 8 seconds.
4. After data has been offloaded and re-launched, thoroughly clean sensor.
 - Clean the body of the logger using soap solution and toothbrush.
 - Clean the sensor using soap solution and a cotton swab or Q-tip. **Do not scrape the sensor.**
 - The logger can be soaked in the vinegar solution to help loosen fouling of calcareous or encrusting organisms.
 - Rinse logger in freshwater and dry.
4. Prep loggers to mitigate fouling.

-
- Wrap body of logger in electrical tape starting at the bottom of the logger and work your way up to the top.
 - Wrap top of logger (sensor) with a small piece of pantyhose.
 5. Re-deploy HOBOLogger by attaching the logger to the PVC pole using 3 zipties as previously described.
 - Allow logger to stabilize (approximately 15 mins).
 6. Take calibration reading:
 - Place YSI probes so that it is close to HOBOLogger but not touching.
 - Ensure there are no air bubbles under the pantyhose near the HOBOLogger sensor.
 - Record temperature and conductivity using YSI.
 - Ensure to record the values, **time**, and location in water quality field notebook. Recording additional water quality metrics such as dissolved oxygen and pH may be beneficial.
 - Ensure to complete post-calibration within 24 hours.

DATA PREPARATION

Find more information on the HOBOWare conductivity assistant here:

<https://www.onsetcomp.com/sites/default/files/resources-documents/15019-E%20Conductivity%20Assistant%20UG.pdf?srsltid=AfmBOopjojEVipcTAPNH94ioSWzgAkq2hySGKQ8aG3cLcxUEUbDwAaac>

1. Open 1 data file at a time in HOBOWare.
2. Go to File, Units, then Plot.
3. Use HOBOWare Conductivity Assistant to input calibration readings (taken at deployment and retrieval) to adjust for drift.
 - Enter YSI readings for conductivity and temperature as well as the time data collected.
4. Save adjusted file as a CSV file to upload into R.

REFERENCES & RESOURCES

Onset Computer Corporation. (n.d.). *HOBO U24 Conductivity Logger (U24-002-C) Manual*. HOBO Data Loggers. <https://www.onsetcomp.com/sites/default/files/resources-documents/16844-G%20U24-002-C%20Manual.pdf>

Onset Computer Corporation. (n.d.). *HOBOWare Pro Conductivity Assistant User's Guide*. HOBO Data Loggers. <https://www.onsetcomp.com/sites/default/files/resources-documents/15019->

[E%20Conductivity%20Assistant%20UG.pdf?srltid=AfmBOopjojEVipcTAPNH94ioSWzgAkq2hySGKQ8aG3cLcxUEUbDwAaac](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353123456/E%20Conductivity%20Assistant%20UG.pdf?srltid=AfmBOopjojEVipcTAPNH94ioSWzgAkq2hySGKQ8aG3cLcxUEUbDwAaac)

Appendix I - Invertebrate Identification Guide

Small Resident Motile Invertebrates

This guide focuses on motile macroinvertebrates (adult size >5mm) typically found occupying oyster reef habitat in Indian River Lagoon (IRL). This guide is meant to help practitioners identify organisms to the family taxonomic level and should not be used for species level identifications. Species are listed and pictured to provide examples of each higher taxonomic group.

All organisms listed have been captured and identified during oyster reef sampling in the Indian River Lagoon published by Boudreaux et al., 2006; Jud and Layman, 2020; and Searles et al., 2022 or captured during sampling in development of this quick assessment guide. All images have been acquired from the Indian River Lagoon Species Inventory unless otherwise specified. Organisms collected during summer 2025 sampling in the development of the IRLNEP Quick Assessment Guide are denoted by an asterisk (*).

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Phylum Arthropoda

Snapping shrimp (family *Alpheidae*: genera *Alpheus* & *Synalpheus*)*

- **1 oversized claw**
- Orbital hood
- At least 11 species in IRL
- Ecological roles: Hunt by stunning/killing prey (worms, small shrimp, crabs, crustaceans, small fish) via claw snap; Can have commensal associations with burrowing species; Healthy reef soundscape.

Bigclaw snapping shrimp (*Alpheus heterochaelis*)

- Dark translucent green w/ orange & blue tipped uropods (tail)
- Snapping claw can be either right or left, attains half of body
- Largest & most colorful

Striped snapping shrimp (*Alpheus formosus*)

- Rostrum usually yellow in adults and entirely yellow in juveniles

Alpheus spp.

Green snapping shrimp (*Alpheus viridari*)

Synalpheus spp.

Palaemonid/Grass Shrimp (family *Palaemonidae*)

- Long pointed rostrum
- 1st pair of legs = clawed, 2nd pair of legs = larger than 1st
- Small size (less than 5cm)
- Ecological role: breakdown of detritus; primary & secondary consumers

Grass shrimp (*Palaemon vulgaris*)

- Transparent besides orange pigmentation on eyestalks

Daggerblade grass shrimp (*Palaemon pugio*)

Leander spp.

Macrobranchium spp.

Palaemon spp.

Periclimenaeus spp.

Periclimenes spp.

Penaeid Shrimp (family *Penaeidae*)

- Prominent rostrum (horn) w/ small teeth upper & lower margins
- 1st 3 pairs walking legs = chelate (pincer like)
- Lack postorbital spines (behind eye)
- Ecological roles: Commercial and recreational fisheries species; Omnivores feeding on living & dead animal & plant material including small benthic invertebrates; Consumed by finfish

Brown shrimp (*Farfantepenaeus aztecus* & *Farfantepenaeus brasiliensis*)

- Antennae significantly longer than body length
- Rostrum (poker on front of head) is slightly shorter than the blades (protruding from mouth)

Pink shrimp (*Panaeus duorarum*)

White shrimp (*Litopenaeus setiferus*)

- Tail has bright yellow/green margins

Mantis Shrimp (family *Squilla*)

- Large (18.5cm)
- 3 pairs thoracic appendages (not 5)
- Ecological role: nocturnal carnivore

Common mantis shrimp (*Squilla empusa*)

Mud Shrimp (family *Upogebia*)

- Large but smaller than mantis shrimp (10cm)
- Ecological role: carnivore that lives in communal burrows

Mud shrimp (*Upogebia* spp.)

Cleaner shrimp (family *Hippolytidae*)

- Small (< 5cm)
- Ecological role: specific to habitat

Zostera shrimp (*Hippolyte zostericola*)

Broken-back shrimp (*Hippolyte spp*)

Latreutus spp

Peppermint shrimp (*Lysmata wurdemanni*)

Swimming crabs (*family Portunidae*)

- Last pair of legs = swimmerets (paddle like appendages)
- Flattened broad carapace
- Ecological role: Opportunistic eaters consuming live prey and decaying matter; Help control populations of mudcrabs, oyster drills, and other gastropods; Commercial and recreational fishery species.

Blue crab (*Callinectes sapidus*)

- Bright blue color along frontal areas

Lesser blue crab (*Callinectes similis*)

- Smoother & more uniform granulated carapace

Ornate blue crab (*Callinectes ornatus*)

Indo-pacific swimming crab (*Charybdis hellerii*)

- A prominent spine on carpus of swimming leg, lighter area on anterior carapace, bristles stopping before the tip of the first male pleopod.

Portunus spp.

Mud crabs (family *Panopeidae*)*

- Carapace usually hexagonal
- Chelipeds (claws) with fingers pointed or spoon-like
- Relatively small size ~ < 50mm
- Ecological role: Feed off encrusting organisms and small animals in reef; Eaten by larger animals; Burrow within oyster reef.
- Difficult to distinguish between *Panopeidae* species. Also difficult to distinguish small stone crabs (*Menippe mercenaria*) and mud crabs (*Panopeidae*).

Flat mud crab (*Eurypanopeus depressus*)

Very common

- Oval and flattened carapace. Carapace has four lateral teeth on both sides and mottled grayish olive or dark olive brown in color. Two dark brown chelipeds (claws), one large and one small. Underneath, the legs and body are light colored (IRL Species Inventory, n.d.).

Asymmetric mud crab (*Eurypanopeus dissimilis*)

Lobate mud crab (*Eurypanopeus abbreviatus*)

Atlantic mud crab (*Panopeus herbstii*)

Very common

- Claws are distinctly unequal in size, body is brownish. Both fingers on each claw are black, and the color of the lower finger often extends up the palm. An enlarged, white tooth is present at the base of the upper finger on the larger claw. 3rd maxilliped, or feeding appendage, is marked with a red spot in males, sometimes in females.
- Largest species of mud crab in region

Image: Tirzah Chichester

Image: Tirzah Chichester

Oystershell mud crab (*Panopeus simpsoni*)

Furrowed mud crab (*Panopeus occidentalis*)

Harris's mud crab (*Rhithropanopeus harrisi*)

- Maximum size 20mm. Olive-green-brownish color, sometimes with dark spots on its carapace.

Smooth mud crab (*Hexapanopeus angustifrons*)

Say's mud crab (*Dyspanopeus sayi*)

Broad-backed mud crab (*Eurytium limosum*)

Stone crab (family *Menippidae*, species: *Menippe mercenaria*)*

- Can grow larger than mud crabs: 127mm carapace
- Claws unequal with black fingers
- Large blunt tooth occurs at base of moveable finger of major claw and another more distally on lower finger
- Adults = brownish tan, juveniles = deep purple
- Juveniles often have striped legs and purple speckled pattern
- Ecological role: Predates upon barnacles and mollusks (strong claws); Oyster predator; Commercial and recreational fishery species.
- Difficult to distinguish small stone crabs (*Menippe mercenaria*) and mud crabs (*Panopeidae*)

Florida stone crab (*Menippe mercenaria*)

Image: Emily Surmont

Image: Emily Surmont

Image: Emily Surmont

Porcelain crabs (family *Porcellanidae*, genus *Petrolisthes*)*

- Unique position of antennae relative to eyes
- Small (1in) and flat bodied
- Ecological role: Filter feeder; non-native species that occur in oyster reef communities

Green porcelain crab (*Petrolisthes armatus*)

- Blue mouth parts and orange spot on chelae.

[Banded porcelain crab (*Petrolisthes galathinus*) – highly unlikely; light color w/ orange stripes]

Hermit crabs (superfamily *Paguroidea*, family *Diogenidae*, genus *Clibanarius*)*

- Occupy mollusk shells
- Eyes mounted on eyestalks
- Ecological role: scavengers that consume detritus

Striped hermit crab (*Clibanarius vittatus*) (common)

- Body is greenish to dark brown with grey or white stripes. Stripes very noticeable on the legs.
- Chelipeds (claws) are equal in size, cylindrical, and covered in blue tubercles. Fingers open horizontally and have several teeth.

Tricolor hermit crab (*Clibanarius tricolor*) (less common)

- Small (only reaches 2cm)
- Blue legs with red banding between each segment

Shore crabs (superfamily *Grapsoidea*, family *Grapsidae*, genus *Pachygrapsus*)*

- Square-shaped carapace
- Eyes located at far corners of carapace
- Ecological roles: detritivores; burrowing

Mottled shore crab (*Pachygrapsus transversus*)

- Dark green to black trapezoid shaped carapace with few spines and oblique lines of fine tubercles or bumps.
- Trapezoid shaped carapace, area between eyes slightly curved.
- Claws brown to pink or cream, smooth upper surface on moveable finger.
- Teeth present on hind margins of largest leg joints.

Dark shore crab (*Pachygrapsus gracilis*)

Mangrove root crab (*Goniopsis cruentata*)

Marsh crab (superfamily *Grapsoidea*, family *Sesarmidae*)*

- Pointed legs for climbing intertidal surfaces
- Square-shaped carapace
- Eyes located at far corners of carapace
- Ecological role: detritivores

Squareback marsh crab (*Armases cinereum*)

- Top margin of upper finger on claw bears small tubercles or bumps
- Last segment of 4th walking leg equipped with black spines on dorsal & ventral surface
- Carapace brown to olive

Mangrove marsh crab (*Sesarma curacaoense*)

-
- Carapace wider than long

Mangrove tree crab (*Aratus pisonii*)

Spider crabs and decorator crabs (superfamily *Majoidea*)*

- Spider-like appearance with round carapace & long legs
- Pointed mouth area
- Ecological role: Scavengers; Prey for other organisms

Doubtful spider crab (*Libinia dubia*)

- Juveniles attach bits of algae and invertebrates to carapace for camouflage
- Adult carapace usually clean
- Long, hooked appendages

Libinia spp.

Clinging crab (*Mithrax spp.*)

Elbow crabs (family *Parthenopidae*)

Pentagon crab (*Heterocrypta granulata*)

- Found on molluscan and other shells

Fiddler crab (family *Ocypodidae*)

- One extremely large claw
- Ecological role: Burrowing; Consumer and prey item.

Uca spp.

Bivalve pea crabs (family *Pinnotheridae*)

- Tiny, round crabs that live commensally inside oyster shells
- Ecological role: Commensal relationship with oysters (may inevitably eat some oyster meat when times are tough)

Pea crab (*Pinnixa* spp.)

*Isopods (order Isopoda)**

- 2 pairs of antennae, body = 7 segments each with own pair walking legs
- Broad flattened appearance (hamburger bun) (amphipods & tanaids = hotdog bun)
- Ecological role: Scavengers; Prey item.

Ligia spp.

Cyathura polita

-
- Size not well-known, Encyclopedia of Life image shows 8mm.

Paradella diane

- Size 2.1- 5.6 mm
- Mottled brown and yellowish white, broad yellowish white patch

Excorallana spp.

Phylum Mollusca

Rock snails (superfamily *Muricoidea*, family *Muricidae*)*

- Raised spire, spiral ridges, axial varices (thickening)
- Ecological role: carnivores & oyster predators- drill into shells & consume soft tissues

Thick-lipped drill (*Eupleura caudata*)

Eupleura spp. (*Eupleura caudata*, *Eupleura sulcidentata*, *Eupleura tampaensis*)

Florida rock snail (*Stramonita haemastoma*, formerly *Thais haemastoma floridana*)

Image: Brenda Bowling, Texas Parks and Wildlife.

Atlantic oyster drill (*Urosalpinx cinerea*)

Image: jaxshells.org, Conchologist of America

Ceriths (superfamily *Cerithioidea*, family *Cerithiidae*)*

- Elongated, sharply conical, grow to ~25mm
- Ecological roles: Algae grazers; Food for predators (crabs, gastropods, horseshoe crabs, stingrays); Transmitter of parasites (nematodes) to predators (mullet, pelicans, cormorants, raccoons)

Florida's Cerith (*Cerithium atratum*)

- Creamy white w/ patches or spiral lines of orange/brown
- Whorls crossed by incised spiral lines forming flat cords of varying length
- Short row of axial riblets below suture
- Spiral cords present

Flyspeck Cerith (*Cerithium muscarum*)

- Small brown “fly specks” form spiral rows
- 9-11 nodule axial ribs, crossed by dotted & dashed spiral lines

Grass cerith (*Bittiolum varium*)

- Aperture notably rounded

Nassa snail (superfamily *Buccinoidea*, family *Nassariidae*)*

Bruised nassa (*Phrontis vibex*)

- Groove in front lower part of shell
- Cone-shaped spiral, white to yellow to light or dark brown
- Ecological role: sand/mud dwelling; Eat carrion and eggs of polychaetes.

Turrid shells (superfamily *Conoidea*, family *Mangeliidae*)

Plicate mangelia (*Pyrgocythara plicosa*)

- Spire ~1/2 length of shell
- Strong indentation internal side of outer lip
- Light-brown to reddish-brown
- 6mm in length

Cerithiopsids (superfamily *Triphoroidea*, family *Cerithiopsidae*)

Green's miniature Cerith (*Cerithiopsis greenii*)

- Shell solid pale brown; Maximum reported size: 4.6mm
- 3 whorled protoconch- 3 rows rounded beads each

Pyramid Snails (superfamily *Pyramidelloidea*, family *Pyramidellidae*)

Impressed odostome (*Boonea impressa*)

- Shell size to 6 mm; white color
- Sculpture of four raised spiral cords separated by deep grooves. Fine axial lines present between cords.
- Ecological role: Ectoparasite on eastern oyster.

Periwinkles (superfamily *Littorinoidea*, family *Littorinidae*)

Marsh periwinkle (*Littorina irrorata*)

- Greyish-white, fine spiral grooves, 5 whorls, pointed spire (20-32mm)
- Outer lip prominent w/ slight flare, fine grooves on inner surface
- Ecological role: Feed on *Spartina*; Eaten by blue crabs, fish, birds, small mammals, diamondback terrapins

Auger snails (superfamily *Conoidea*, family *Terebridae*)

Salle's auger snail (*Hastula salleana*)

- Up to 40mm
- Ecological role: feed on polychaetes using toxins

Wentletraps (superfamily *Epitonioidae*, family *Epitoniidae*)

- Spiral staircase
- Ecological role: predate upon cnidarians (anemones)

Epitonium spp.

Dove snails (superfamily *Buccinoidea*, family *Columbellidae*)

Astyris lunata

- 3 series of hook-shaped bands in middle & at ends.
- Ecological role: preys on encrusting ascidians & byozoans

Greedy dovesnail (*Costoanachis avara*)

- 8-19mm length

Nerite (superfamily *Neritoidea*, family *Neritidae*)*

- Round, variably patterned shells
- Ecological role: algae grazer

Clench's nerite snail (*Vitta clenchi*, formerly *Neritina clenchi*)

Virgin nerite (*Vitta virginea*)

Antillean nerite (*Nerita fulgurans*)

Checked nerite (*Nerita tessellata*)

Bubble shells (superfamily *Bulloidea*, family *Bullidae*)

Common Atlantic bubble (*Bulla striata*)

- Smooth oval shell

-
- Ecological role: feeds on molluscs

Minute sea snails (family *Caecidae*)

Beautiful caecum (*Caecum pulchellum*)

- Maximum recorded length 4.5mm

Slipper snails (superfamily *Calyptraeoidea*, family *Calyptraeidae*)*

Spotted slipper snail (*Crepidula maculosa*)

- Maximum length 35mm

Dendrodoris sea slugs (Superfamily *Phyllidioidea*, family *Dendrodorididae*)

- Ecological role: predate upon sponges

Lemon drop sea slug (*Doriopsilla pharpa*) (50-70mm)

Venus clams (superfamily *Veneroidea*, family *Veneridae*)

- Bivalves, rounded or oval shells, radial ornamentation
- Umbo inturned towards anterior end
- Ecological role: Burrowers; Human fisheries

Hard clam & Southern hard clam (*Mercenaria mercenaria*, *Mercenaria campechiensis*)

Razor clam (*Tagelus* spp.)

Dwarf surf clam (superfamily *Mactroidea*, family *Mactridae*, *Mulinia lateralis*)*

- Bivalve with unique triangular shape
- Ecological role: Burrower

Lucinid clam (superfamily *Lucinoidea*, family *Lucinidae*)*

- Bivalve with thin rounded shell, typically white
- Ecological role: Burrower; Important in seagrass ecosystems.

Phylum Annelida

Class Polychaeta*

- Segmented worms with paired legs on most segments
- Well-developed head

-
- Ecological roles: Burrowing species; food for other organisms

Green oyster worm (family *Phyllodoce*, *Nereiphylla fragilis* (*Phyllodoce fragilis*))

Common bloodworm (family *Eunicidae*, *Marphysa sanguinea*)

Clam worm (family *Nereididae*, *Alitta succinea*)

*Order Sipuncula**

- Unsegmented peanut worm
- Can retract into round shape (resembling a peanut)
- Ecological role: Deposit feeders

Peanut worm (Order *Sipuncula*)

Platyhelminthes

Oyster leech (superfamily *Stylochoidea*, family *Stylochidae*, genus *Stylochus*)*

- Brown flatworm
- Ecological role: Feed on oysters

Phylum Echinodermata

Brittle stars (class *Ophiuroidea*)

- 5 equal arms and central disk
- Ecological role: Family *Amphiuridae* & *Ophionereididae*: feed on organic matter & algae on sediment surface

Brooding brittle star (family *Amphiuridae*, *Amphipholis squamata*)

Long-armed burrowing brittle star (family *Amphiuridae*, *Amphiodia pulchella*)

Burrowing brittle stars (family *Amphiuridae*)

Reticulated brittle star (family *Ophionereididae*, *Ophionereis reticulata*)

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Appendix J - Fish Identification Guide

Small Resident Fish

This guide focuses on resident fish typically found occupying oyster reef habitat in Indian River Lagoon (IRL). This guide is meant to help practitioners identify organisms to the family taxonomic level and should not be used for species level identifications. Species are listed and pictured to provide examples of each higher taxonomic group.

All organisms listed have been captured and identified during oyster reef sampling in the Indian River Lagoon published by Boudreaux et al., 2006; Jud and Layman, 2020; and Searles et al., 2022 or captured during sampling in development of this quick assessment guide. All images have been acquired from the Indian River Lagoon Species Inventory unless otherwise specified. Organisms collected during summer 2025 sampling in the development of the IRLNEP Quick Assessment Guide are denoted by an asterisk (*).

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Blennies (family Blenniidae)

- One long continuous dorsal fin
- Curved body posture
- “Perching” behavior with 2 separate pelvic fins
- Small scales or lack scales
- Up to 20cm
- Ecological role: benthic algae eaters

Highfin Blenny (*Lupinoblennius nicholsi*)

Florida blenny (*Chasmodes saburrae*)

Oyster blenny (*Hypleurochilus aequipinnis*) Rosy blenny (*Malacoctenus macropus*)

Freckled blenny (*Hypsoblennius ionthas*)

*Gobies (family Gobiidae)**

- 2 separate dorsal fins
- Fused pelvic fins that create suction cup to attach to bottom
- Straight/rigid body shape
- Scaled
- Up to 60cm
- Ecological role: create burrows (may share with shrimp)

Crested Goby (*Lophogobius cyprinoides*)

Frillfin Goby (*Bathygobius soporator*)

Naked Goby (*Gobiosoma bosc*)

Darter goby (*Gobionellus boleosoma*)

Code goby (*Gobiosoma robustum*)

Pupfish (superfamily Cyprinodontiformes, family Cyprinodontidae)

Sheepshead minnow (*Cyprinodon variegatus*)

Goldspotted killifish (*Floridichthys carpio*)

Topminnows & killifishes (superfamily Cyprinodontiformes, family Fundulidae)

Gulf killifish (*Fundulus grandis*)

Rainwater killifish (*Lucania parva*)

Mollies (family Poecilia)

Sailfin molly (*Poecilia latipinna*)

Sleeper gobies (family Eleotridae)

Emerald sleeper (*Eretelis smaragdus*)

Toadfish (family Batrachoididae)

Oyster toadfish (*Opsanus tau*)

*Clingfishes (family Gobiesocidae)**

Skilletfish (*Gobiesox strumosus*)

- Sucking disk ventral side
- 6 faint lines radiate from eye
- 40-45mm reproductive size

Mojarra (family Gerreidae)

Irish pompano (*Diapterus auratus*)

Mojarra (*Eucinostomus sp.*)

Porgies (family Sparidae)

Sheepshead (*Archosargus probatocephalus*)

Pinfish (Lagodon rhomboides)

Drums & croakers (family Sciaenidae)

Silver perch (*Bairdiella chrysoura*)

Grunts (family Haemulon)

French grunt (*Haemulon flavolineatum*)

Scaled-fin grunts (*Haemulon* spp.)

Snapper (family Lutjanidae)

- **10 dorsal spines**

Gray snapper (*Lutjanus griseus*)

Candy striper (*Lutjanus synagris*)

Mullet (family Mugilidae)

Striped mullet (*Mugil cephalus*)

White mullet (*Mugil curema*)

Large tooth flounders (family Paralichthyidae)

Gulf flounder (*Paralichthys albigutta*)

Southern flounder

Grouper (family Epinephelidae)
Goliath grouper (Epinephelus itajara)

Pipefish (family Syngnathidae)
Gulf pipefish (Syngnathus scovelli)

*Worm eels (Family Ophichthidae, Subfamily Myrophinae)**
Speckled worm eel (Myrophis punctatus)

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